

Workshop Report

Sociobioeconomies and Conservation Finance in the Amazon

This document brings together the debates and reflections of the participants of the workshop "Sociobioeconomies and Conservation Finance in the Amazon."

This is the **Report of Workshop 1** of the Project "Power of Connections: Harvesting Lessons and Strengthening Coalitions for the Conservation of the Amazon".

February 2025

Report of the Workshop '**Sociobioeconomies and Conservation Finance in the Amazon,**' held between May 28 and 31, 2025 in Nazaré Paulista, São Paulo, Brazil.

Organization: University of Florida Tropical Development and Conservation Program (TCD/UF), in collaboration with the Moore Foundation.

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1. Pan-Amazonia. 2. Community entrepreneurship. 3. Value chains. 4. Impact financing. 5. Collaborative development models

Table of Contents

Presentation	5
Workshop organization process	8
Workshop objectives	8
Agenda	9
Participants and their origins	12
Participant expectations	14
Collective definitions	15
What do we mean by Sociobioeconomies and Conservation Finance?	15
Collective reflections	21
Exploring sociobioeconomies and conservation finance from multiple perspectives 23	
Sociobioeconomies from the perspective of non-governmental organizations	25
Financing and economic sustainability	27
Challenges and strategies to overcome.....	29
Sociobioeconomies from the perspective of communities	30
ASPROC Experience.....	31
Kallari's Experience	32
The challenges and strategies	33
Practices and challenges in the construction of an Amazonian sociobioeconomy	35
Initiatives and context	35
Inclusion and local transformations	38
Greenwashing and value capture	39
Conservation Finance	40
Conscious financing.....	40
Diversity of funds, risks, and the challenge of modernizing the financial architecture.....	41
Bringing together conservation finance and sociobioeconomy	45
Scalable, ethical, inclusive, and equitable approaches	48
Collective reflections	55
Gender, social equity, and territorial wellbeing in Conservation Finance and Sociobioeconomies	58
Network Mapping	65
Overview of mapped networks	66
Collective reflections on the value of networks	67
Ways to scale the Amazonian sociobioeconomy: financing, autonomy and strategic alliances	68
Workshop Closing	76
Appendix	79

List of acronyms and abbreviations

ATL	Acampamento Terra Livre
ANMIGA	Articulação Nacional das Mulheres Indígenas Guerreiras da Ancestralidade
BNDES	National Bank for Economic and Social Development
CIP	International Potato Center
CGIAR	Consultative Group on International Agricultural Research
COP	Conference of the Parties to the United Nations
ESCAS	School of Environmental Conservation and Sustainability
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
FIINSA	Festival of Impact Investments and Sustainable Business in the Amazon
FUNBIO	Brazilian Biodiversity Fund
GEF	Global Environment Facility
GIZ	German Agency for International Cooperation
IBAMA	Brazilian Institute of the Environment
MIT	Massachusetts Institute of Technology
Moore	Gordon and Betty Moore Foundation
NDC	Nationally Determined Contributions
NGO	Non-governmental organization
R&D	Research & Development
RD&I	Research, Development and Innovation
PNAE	Brazilian School Feeding Program
IPÊ	Instituto de Pesquisas Ecológicas
PES	Payment for environmental services
REDD	Reducing emissions from deforestation and forest degradation
RDS	Sustainable Development Reserve
TAC	Adjustment of Conduct Period
TCD	Conservation and Tropical Development Studies Program
UF	University of Florida
VET	Total Economic Value

Presentation

Between May 28 and 31, 2025, in Nazaré Paulista (SP), Brazil, community leaders, researchers, investors, and representatives of public and private organizations met at the *Workshop on Sociobioeconomies and Conservation Finance in the Amazon*. This document is a record of the ideas, tensions, and paths that emerged in search of a more just economy rooted in the forest.

The workshop was held within the framework of the *Power of Connections – Harvesting Lessons and Strengthening Connections for the Conservation of the Amazon* project, an initiative of the Tropical Conservation and Development Program (TCD) of the University of Florida (UF), in collaboration with the Institute for Ecological Research (IPÊ) and with financial support from the Gordon and Betty Moore Foundation.

The project is based on the premise that the Amazon, one of the most biodiverse and relevant ecosystems on the planet, is deeply connected to global social, political, and economic systems. Changes in international policies, investment decisions, or consumption patterns in other parts of the world directly affect Amazonian peoples and territories. Therefore, the central proposal of the project is to promote collective learning processes and strengthen coalitions and collaboration networks between Pan-Amazonian countries, connecting academic, traditional and community knowledge.

The project recognizes that effective conservation of the Amazon can only be achieved with the Amazonians and not in spite of them. Thus, the knowledge, practices and ways of life developed by indigenous peoples, traditional communities and local organizations, which offer innovative and replicable solutions to sustainability challenges, are valued.

The project began in January 2025 and ends in September 2026 and includes an international conference in Gainesville (USA) in February 2026 with the participation of thematic leaders and representatives of the partners involved. During this period, five thematic workshops will be held in different countries of the Amazon:

1. Sociobioeconomies and conservation finance (Brazil, May 2025);
2. Reshaping institutions for the next generation of leaders in amazon conservation (Bolivia, July 2025);
3. Collaborative management focused on Indigenous Peoples and Local Communities (Brazil, September 2025);
4. Innovations in the research process (Peru, December 2025);
5. Indigenous rights and governance instruments (Ecuador, January 2025).

The workshop featured in this article was the first of the cycle, focused on scaling up sociobioeconomies and discussing financing mechanisms for conservation. Representatives of civil society organizations, community associations, universities and the private sector participated, providing a plural space for exchange, listening and collective construction.

During the opening of the event, researcher Karen Kainer, one of the coordinators of the project, reinforced the idea that it is a global-local effort, with an impact not only on the Amazon, but also

on international agendas. For this reason, the project aims to share the solutions created by the Amazonian peoples, connecting experiences and multiplying paths for conservation and sustainable territorial development.

Here we highlight the main activities, moments, and content discussed by the participants and recorded by the University of Florida team. We hope that this information can contribute to the strengthening of governance and socioenvironmental development processes in the region.

Happy reading!

Workshop organization process

This workshop, like the other four thematic workshops of the POC project, was the result of collaboration between the thematic leaders and the University of Florida (UF) team. The thematic leaders were selected several months in advance for their extensive experience in the Amazon and in the specific theme of the workshop. From then on, through weekly meetings, they and the UF team shaped the event: first by jointly defining the objectives and then by drawing up the list of participants, selected for the relevance of their knowledge and their approach to action.

A few months before the workshop, the facilitation team was also formed, led by two people: the facilitator of the UF team and an external facilitator from an Amazonian country; the latter also identified by the workshop organizing team. With the objectives defined and the participants confirmed, this team designed the agenda, which was subsequently reviewed and validated by the entire organizing group.

Figure 1 Detailed description of the process of organizing the workshops held within the framework of the "Power of Connections" project.

During the workshop, facilitation was carried out with a flexible and participatory approach, ensuring that each participant could contribute meaningfully to the discussions. Each day, and even sometimes during the sessions, the organizing team met briefly to reflect, evaluate the ongoing process and, if necessary, make adjustments to the agenda along the way. Finally, after the workshop, the organizing team worked on the results, which were shared with the participants for validation in a virtual meeting. This was an iterative process, which was refined and strengthened with each subsequent workshop.

Workshop objectives

The main objective of the workshop was to promote a space for cross-border and intercultural dialogue between community leaders, researchers, NGO representatives, the private sector and

public institutions from different Pan-Amazonian countries. The proposal was to promote the exchange of experiences, collective reflection, and the construction of connections around two major thematic axes: sociobioeconomies and Conservation Finance.

The organizers highlighted that, although these issues have gained singular relevance in the Amazon in recent years, they are rarely discussed together in an articulated way. Therefore, the workshop had as an innovation the integrated approach of these two fields, seeking to understand how they can complement each other to strengthen sustainable development models that reconcile conservation and socioeconomic justice and effectiveness.

Two main objectives were set to guide the work throughout the week:

1. Exchange and disseminate experiences on innovative and successful initiatives in sociobioeconomy and financing for conservation in the Amazon;
2. Strengthen and catalyze existing collaboration networks between Amazonian countries, stimulating partnerships and joint projects that expand the territorial impact of the experiences discussed.

Agenda

The workshop was structured around four progressive axes, each with a central theme:

Day 1: Concepts and definitions

The group focused on the challenge of building a shared definition of sociobioeconomy, recognizing the diversity of interpretations and experiences that exist in different Amazonian contexts.

Day 2: Case Studies and Cross-Interviews

Each participant had the opportunity to present, in an interview format, the work they do in their territories and institutions, promoting attentive listening and mutual learning between sectors (communities, NGOs, private sector and academia).

Day 3: Challenges to Achieving Scale

The aim was to reflect on what it means to scale up sociobioeconomies, whether in terms of impact, territorial coverage, number of beneficiaries or political influence, and what are the obstacles faced in this process.

Day 4: Future paths and Joint proposals

On the last day, participants discussed strategies for the continuity of collaboration, the identification of synergies and proposals that can be carried out collectively, including in subsequent project workshops.

Throughout the workshop, active listening was valued as the main methodology, in an environment designed to be informal, welcoming, and horizontal, respecting the different rhythms and languages (Portuguese, Spanish and English). The organizers reinforced the importance of each participant contributing to and taking with them new ideas, enriching perspectives and, above all, possible alliances for future actions. A summary of the program and topics is described in Table 1. The full and detailed schedule is in Appendix A.

Table 1 Summary of the complete program of the workshop 'Sociobioeconomies and Conservation Finance'

Day 1 – May 28, 2025 Guidelines and Trust Building
<p>MORNING</p> <p>7:30-8:20 Breakfast</p> <p>8:30 Opening</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Welcome to IPÊ from Claudio and Suzana Padua (15 min.) • Welcome by Karen Kainer from UF/Moore (10 min.) • Introducing the facilitators – Denyse Mello and Jon Dain <p>09:00 Participant personal presentations</p> <p>09:30 Welcome by thematic leaders Claudio Padua (IPE - Brazil) and Trent Blare (International Potato Center - Ecuador) (10 min)</p> <p>9:45 Project summary and workshop context by Karen Kainer</p> <p>10:05 Objectives, agenda, and guiding questions of the workshop</p> <p>10:50 Definition of terms: "sociobioeconomy" and Conservation Finance</p> <p>AFTERNOON</p> <p>12:00 Lunch</p> <p>14:00 Plenary session and presentation of the groups</p> <p>15.50 Plenary discussion on commonalities between the concepts of sociobioeconomy and conservation finance</p> <p>16:45-17:00 Conclusion</p> <p>19:00 Dinner</p>
Day 2 – May 29, 2025 Exploring the Challenges: Identifying Tensions and Leverage Points
<p>MORNING</p> <p>7:30-8:20 Breakfast</p> <p>8:30 Start</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Brief Review of Day I and Introduction to the Day II Agenda + Guiding Questions <p>09:00 Panel Panel: Trent Blare interviews NGO representatives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Carlos Koury - IDESAM • Paulina Espin – TRIAS Ecuador <p>09:40 Panel: Claudio Padua interviews community representatives</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adevaldo Dias – Memorial Chico Mendes • Ruth Cayapa – Kallari Association <p>11:00 Panel: Trent Blare interviews private sector representatives</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Andrea Ortiz de Zevallos – Despensa Amazónica • Claudio Padua – Biofilolica and IPÊ <p>AFTERNOON</p> <p>12:00 Lunch</p> <p>13:50 Panel: Claudio Padua interviews private sector /conservation finance representatives</p>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Marcelo Cwerner – Amazon Investor Coalition • Manoel Serrão Bores de Sampaio - FUNBIO <p>14:55 Panel: Pilar Useche interviews researchers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • David Solano Cornejo • Renato Farias <p>16:05 Analysis of the panel interviews (in groups), identifying what worked or did not work among the initiatives presented</p> <p>16:40 Plenary: the groups present their conclusions</p> <p>17:15 Final Discussions and Conclusion</p> <p>19:00 Dinner</p> <p>Conviviality at 20:00</p>
<p>Day 3, May 30, 2025 Scalable, ethical, inclusive, and equitable approaches</p>
<p>MORNING</p> <p>7:30-8:20 Breakfast</p> <p>8:30 am Start</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Review of the previous day and presentation of the third day agenda <p>08:45 Group Activity: Discussion of previous day's sessions</p> <p>09:35 Plenary debate</p> <p>10:40 Panel: Pilar Useche interviews participants on gender, equity, territoriality and integration</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mayra Esseboom – Agricultural Research Center in Suriname • Vanda Witoto – Witoto Institute • Antonio Loboguerero - Etnollano Foundation <p>AFTERNOON</p> <p>12:00 Lunch</p> <p>13:45 Plenary – Harvesting lessons from the initiatives presented in the panels: challenges/tensions for the scalability of sociobioeconomies</p> <p>15:45 Mapping collaborative networks, coalitions and alliances</p> <p>17:30 Discussions and final conclusions</p> <p>19:00 Dinner</p>
<p>Day 4 – May 31, 2025 From inspiration to action</p>
<p>MORNING</p> <p>7:30-8:20 Breakfast</p> <p>8:30 Start</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Review of the previous day and presentation of the fourth day agenda <p>09:15 Facilitated plenary: Resources for scaling and moving forward</p> <p>11:00 Summary and conclusions</p> <p>12:25 Closing</p>

Participants and their origins

The workshop featured a diverse group of 24 participants who live and work on issues of sociobiodiversity and Conservation Finance in the Amazon region. Participants were from non-governmental organizations (NGOs), universities, communities, and the private sector.

Table 2 Complete list of participants present at the workshop 'Sociobioeconomies and Conservation Finance'.

Name	Institution	Country of operation	Email
Adevaldo Dias da Costa	Memorial Chico Mendes	Brazil	adevaldo13@hotmail.com
Claudio Padua	Institute for Ecological Research - IPÊ	Brazil	cpadua@ipe.org.br
Andrea Ortiz de Zevallos	Despensa Amazónica	Peru	andrea@despensamazonica.org
Trent Blare	International Potato Center - CIP/CGIAR	Ecuador	trent.blare@cgiar.org
Antonio Loboguerrero	Etnollano Foundation	Colombia	antonio@fundacionetnollano.org
Carlos Gabriel Koury	Institute for Conservation and Sustainable Development - Idesam	Brazil	carlosgabriel@idesam.org
Ana Luiza Violato Espada	University of Florida - UF	Brazil	violatoespada@ufl.edu
David Solano Cornejo	Universidad Peruana de Ciencias Aplicadas - UPC	Peru	dadadi96@gmail.com
Denyse Mello	Consultant	Brazil	d.mello@cifor-icraf.org
Floriana Breyer	Institute for Ecological Research - IPÊ	Brazil	floriana.breyer@ipe.org.br
Jonathan Dain	University of Florida - UF	USA	jdain@latam.ufl.edu
Angelica Gouveia	University of Florida - UF	Brazil	angelica.gouveia@ufl.edu
Manoel Serrão	Brazilian Biodiversity Fund - FUNBIO	Brazil	manoel.serrao@FUNBIO.org.br
Marcelo Cwener	Amazon Investor Coalition	Brazil	marcelo.cwerner@gmail.com
Mayra Esseboom	Agricultural Research Center in Suriname - CELOS	Suriname	m.esseboom@gmail.com
Natali Silva	Imaflora/Emerging Wildlife Leaders in the Wildlife Conservation Network - WCN	Brazil	Natali@imaflora.org
Paulina Espín	NGO Trias	Ecuador	paulina.espin@trias.ngo
Karen Kainer	University of Florida - UF	USA	kkainer@ufl.edu

Renato Farias	TRUST Consulting	Brazil	renato@consultoriaturst.com
Ruth Cayapa	Agro-Artisan Association for the Production of Agricultural, Livestock and Fish Goods of Napo "Kallari"	Ecuador	presidencia@kallari.com.ec
Suzana Padua	Institute for Ecological Research - IPÊ	Brazil	suzana@ipe.org.br
Pilar Useche	University of Florida - UF	Colombia	useche@ufl.edu
Vanessa Luna	University of Florida - UF	Peru	lunacelino.dv@ufl.edu
Vanda Witoto	Witoto Institute	Brazil	vandawitoto@gmail.com

The round of presentations was based on a map of the Amazon biome, in which each participant used small colored notes to indicate their origin and area of operation in the Amazon (Figure 2). The workshop was attended by representatives from all Amazonian countries, except Bolivia, Venezuela and Guyana.

Figure 2 Origin and area of activity of the workshop participants. Colors indicate countries of operation: blue, Ecuador; green, Colombia and Suriname; Rosa, Peru; and yellow, Brazil.

Participant expectations

At the beginning of the workshop, participants shared their expectations for the event, revealing a great diversity of interests and motivations, but also a convergence around key issues to strengthen the sociobioeconomy in the Amazon.

Figure 3 Participant during the exchange of expectations for the workshop.

One of the main foci was the exchange of experiences and collective learning, with an interest in learning about good practices, mistakes and innovations in progress in different Amazonian territories. Many expressed a desire to learn from initiatives implemented in other countries, especially those that involve gender integration, youth, and overcoming challenges such as illegal activities, neo-extractivism, and pressure for monocultures.

Another recurring theme was the creation and strengthening of collaboration networks between Pan-Amazonian actors. Participants showed great interest in establishing institutional partnerships, promoting exchanges, and expanding dialogue. The idea of building alliances for transnational projects and promoting networking was present in several testimonies.

The expectations also reflected the need to deepen the conceptual and practical understanding of sociobioeconomy, including its viability in complex contexts and its insertion into the formal economic system. Participants questioned how to make this model more effective, inclusive, and connected to public policies, credit systems, and financing strategies.

In this sense, access to finance and valuation of forest products appeared as strategic issues. Participants were motivated to understand how carbon projects, climate funds, and new forms of investment can support the sociobioeconomy, as well as strategies to add value to products and redesign the narrative of risk associated with investing in the Amazon.

Other points highlighted by participants included the need to understand regulatory barriers, sharing governance models that are respectful of local communities, and strengthening institutions in their own territories. Finally, concern arose about the inclusion of vulnerable populations, especially in urban contexts, which broadened the scope of sociobioeconomy as a transformative and non-exclusive proposal.

Table 3 Categories of participants' expectations shared at the beginning of the workshop.

Category	Related Topics and Expectations
1. Exchange of experiences and learning	Learn about good practices and failures, learn from other countries and territories, access inspiring ideas, connect with universities and researchers.
2. Pan-Amazonian networks and alliances	Create and strengthen collaboration networks, promote exchanges, form alliances for projects, cooperation between communities and institutions.
3. Strengthening the sociobioeconomy	Debate and deepen the concept, apply it to challenging contexts (gender, youth, violence), avoid monocultures, think about inclusion or systemic transformation.
4. Value added and value chains	Adding value to forest products, avoiding neo-extractivism, connecting production chains with markets, repositioning investment risk.
5. Financing and formal economy	Understand how to access credit and climate finance, integrate the sociobioeconomy into the formal economy, accelerate financing and innovation.
6. Policies and governance	Understand regulatory barriers, discuss scale and impact models, reflect on prioritization and systemic transformation.
7. Inclusion and socioenvironmental justice	Include urban and vulnerable populations, consider gender and youth issues, and address illegal economies through sociobioeconomy.

Collective definitions

What do we mean by Sociobioeconomies and Conservation Finance?

The workshop began with a reflective and participatory activity, aimed at the collective construction of meanings around two central concepts of the meeting: Sociobioeconomies and

Conservation Finance. Initially, participants were invited to individually write down what they each understood by these terms, both from their personal perspective and from the performance of their organizations.

Figure 4 Participants during an individual moment of reflection on the definition of the terms that guide the workshop.

The activity was piloted by four guiding questions:

1. What does sociobioeconomy mean for you and your organization?
2. What does conservation finance mean for you and your organization?
3. What is your personal connection to these issues?
4. What do you bring to the workshop to share with the other participants?

After this stage, the participants met in small groups, by country, to share their reflections and build collective definitions.

Figure 5 Participants during a group discussion on sociobioeconomy concepts.

The group made up of participants from Peru stressed that the sociobioeconomy must start from the sustainable use of nature, incorporating respect for biodiversity, production cycles and local knowledge. For them, overcoming productive gaps, as well as a fair connection with markets, are essential components to guarantee the equitable distribution of the benefits derived from this economy.

The group of participants from Ecuador, for their part, defined the sociobioeconomy as a system of exchanges based on the responsible use of natural resources, aimed at generating decent income and the wellbeing of communities. Cultural diversity and the conservation of ecosystems were identified as inseparable dimensions of this economic practice. Reflecting on Conservation Finance, they emphasized the importance of economic recognition of ecosystem services and the need to integrate decision-making with equity criteria. The group emphasized that sociobioeconomy is an ancestral practice that is now acquiring a contemporary name, and its dissemination requires dialogue with different audiences, from producers to academics. According to the group, this economy already exists and the challenge is to give it visibility to other possible forms of recognition and financing, which are not limited to the logic of consumption of the global North.

In the Suriname group, they emphasized that sociobioeconomy must articulate three fundamental dimensions: economic, social, and biological. They argued that generating income cannot be the only objective; it also is necessary to guarantee social responsibility and sustainability. They also reflected on forms of collective organization and how to reconcile them with alternative ways of life, such as those of subsistence producers and specific

communities such as Mennonites. Regarding the financing of conservation, they argued that these should be aligned with indigenous and community values, so that insertion in the market does not become a factor of exploitation or depletion of daily community life.

Figure 6 Participants during the presentation of the conclusions of the discussion in small groups.

The group of participants from Colombia affirmed that there is not a single sociobioeconomy, but multiple expressions based on the diversity of principles, territories and values. For them, this economy should be at the service of nature, not the other way around, and present itself as an alternative to conventional models; sociobioeconomies propose an economy of abundance. They highlighted the collective nature and appreciation of sharing, reciprocity, and complementarity. They also stressed that the sociobioeconomy must promote collective wellbeing, autonomy, intercultural dialogue, and the appreciation of local knowledge and ecosystem services. They stressed that it is necessary to promote co-innovation processes that combine ancestral technologies with modern innovations, including challenging conventional systems of industrial innovation.

The Brazilian participants formed two groups. The first group defined the sociobioeconomy as a set of economic activities that strengthen the relationship between humans and nature, promoting biodiversity conservation, wellbeing, and the generation of fair income. There was consensus on the need for these activities to be profitable as well, arguing that economic viability is essential to ensure investment and market access. The definition of Conservation Finance, in turn, revolved around the idea of financial mechanisms that should be accessible, fair, and geared towards promoting and protecting nature. Participants underlined the importance of considering interest rates and barriers to entry, which are often insurmountable. They also stressed that it is important to explicitly state which social groups are intended to be reached with this financing to avoid the commonplace exclusion of the most vulnerable. The breadth of the terms was also discussed, paying attention to the risk of appropriation by sectors that contradict its principles, such as soy and livestock.

Figure 7 Participants constructing definitions of Sociobioeconomies and Conservation Finance.

In the second Brazilian group, sociobioeconomy was understood as part of a broader system – social, environmental and economic – oriented to the wellbeing of vulnerable populations, based on the sustainable use of natural resources, and with effective results for conservation. They stressed that the bioeconomy must respect the limits of the territory and recognize existing economies, avoiding the reproduction of extractive or exploitative logics. Participants discussed the true limits of the sociobioeconomy in the face of pressures from broader economic systems and environmental and social threats, and proposed that it be understood in the context of a more complex and interconnected system.

Regarding Conservation Finance, the group proposed that these are public or private contributions, reimbursable or not, that allow conservation actions and reduce inequalities. The group stressed that it is essential that these investments promote social justice, as those who conserve the most are often those who live in the greatest poverty and exclusion. They reflected on the bureaucratic challenges that hinder access to resources for conservation, comparing them to the ease of obtaining investments that result in environmental degradation. They also warned about the symbolic construction of conservation as something associated with poverty and stressed the importance of valuing the strategic role of the sociobioeconomy in times of crisis, such as locally- and regionally-generated supplies during the truckers' strike in Brazil.

Figure 8 Participants during small group discussions.

The definitions presented by the groups demonstrate the conceptual richness and plurality of experiences around the two central axes of the workshop. Although each group had developed a situated and contextualized understanding, converging elements emerged: sociobioeconomy is recognized as an existing practice, based on local knowledge, collectivity, and the sustainable use of natural resources, while conservation finance is seen as an instrument that must ensure fair, accessible, and effective support to communities and initiatives that promote conservation in the Amazon. The reflections of the participants also point to the urgency of protecting these concepts from opportunistic uses, reaffirming their commitment to equity, biodiversity, and the profound transformation of current economic models.

Table 4 Summary of the definitions of Sociobioeconomies and Conservation Finance presented during the workshop.

Country	Definition of Sociobioeconomy	Definition of Conservation Finance
Peru	Sustainable use of nature in relation to biodiversity, production cycles, and local knowledge. Equitable distribution of benefits and fair linkages with markets.	Ensure that economic agents have financial resources (non-reimbursable and reimbursable) to preserve ecosystem services and to guarantee their existence for future generations.
Colombia	Multiple expressions based on the diversity of values and territories. Economy of abundance focused on	Promotion of autonomy, appreciation of local knowledge, and co-innovation between ancestral and modern technology.

	nature and collective wellbeing, with intercultural dialogue.	
Ecuador	A system of exchanges based on the responsible use of natural resources, with a focus on a dignified income, wellbeing, cultural diversity, and ecosystem conservation.	Economic recognition of ecosystem services and the need to integrate decision-making with equity criteria.
Suriname	Articulation of the economic, social, and biological dimensions. Income generation with social responsibility and sustainability, respecting alternative ways of life.	Alignment with Indigenous and community values, preventing the market from exploitation or depletion of daily community life.
Brazil 1	A set of economic activities that strengthen the relationship between human beings and nature, promoting the conservation of biodiversity, wellbeing, and the generation of fair income.	Accessible, fair, and explicit financial mechanisms with respect to the social groups benefited. Beware of embezzlement by contradictory sectors.
Brazil 2	It is part of a broader system – social, environmental and economic – oriented to the wellbeing of vulnerable populations, based on the sustainable use of natural resources and with effective results for conservation.	Contributions to investment – public or private, reimbursable or not – that enable actions to conserve nature and reduce inequalities.

Collective reflections

After the presentation of the definitions constructed by each group, the participants met to have an open discussion about what stood out to them most in the different contributions and what common points could be identified. The dialogue revealed the complexity of the issue and the multiplicity of interpretations of Sociobioeconomies and Conservation Finance, reinforcing that these are concepts under construction, marked by disputes, different worldviews, and distinct territorial experiences.

The group stressed that, by positioning themselves as active agents in the formulation of the concept of sociobioeconomy, it is essential that this process incorporates the historical pains of the peoples exploited by the dominant economic models. Participants recognized that every economy is inevitably related to the market, but that the difference lies in the ability to propose alternatives that highlight what needs to be transformed, both in power relations and in productive paradigms. Sociobioeconomy, from this perspective, must go beyond technical solutions, being a political and ethical response rooted in territorial and historical experiences.

Participants emphasized that classical paradigms of economics (such as capitalism and socialism) belong to a matrix of Western thought and therefore do not fully respond to the realities of the Amazon and other territories. In this context, the participants defended the sociobioeconomy as a rescue of traditional knowledge and ancestral ways of life, which already operated according to integrated logics of care for the environment and social justice.

Therefore, it is a matter of recognizing and strengthening non-Western knowledge systems as legitimate bases for building a new economy.

The discussion advanced towards international negotiation spaces, such as the Conference of the Parties (COP), which will have its next edition in the Amazon (November 2026). The collective recognized the symbolic opportunity of this event, but expressed strong skepticism about its actual effectiveness. Despite their visibility, these forums were seen as often excluding the voices most directly involved in defending territories, especially indigenous peoples, women, and black populations. Participants reiterated the need to guarantee decision-making spaces for these voices and demand structured public policies that sustain deep and lasting transformations.

The workshop also addressed ways to strengthen civil society's advocacy capacity. Participants highlighted the importance of forming structured alliances, networks of networks and regional articulations capable of dialogue with governments and directly influencing agendas. It was noted that the organization of civil society in permanent and coordinated structures was essential to ensure continuity and impact. Participants defended investment in grassroots work and the strengthening of local networks as mechanisms to guarantee the rooting and legitimacy of sociobioeconomy proposals.

A central point of the group discussion was the challenge of expanding the mobilization around sociobioeconomies. Participant reflection revolved around the idea of making this concept as visible as the dominant narratives of agribusiness, which operate with a heavy investment in communication. The provocation arose: Would it be possible to transform conservation and sustainable ways of living into something as "popular" as agro-industrial media campaigns? The group's response was realistic: There is an abundance of knowledge, but there is a lack of strategic articulation and leadership that integrates efforts and communicates the proposal clearly. The group noted an urgent need for long-term collective coordination and planning.

Figure 9 Panel with the definitions of Sociobioeconomies and Conservation Finance presented by the participants.

The group criticized the actions of universities, which often accumulate knowledge without distributing it in an accessible or committed way. It was mentioned that while researchers can contribute technically, rarely is external funding applied to autonomous initiatives that engage effectively with communities and territories. Therefore, the conceptual construction of sociobioeconomy must be clear, democratic, and available to the multiple social actors that build it in practice.

Another concern noted by participants was the waste of resources and efforts on specific initiatives, without continuity. Participants articulated several examples of interrupted projects, with abandoned structures and unsustainable impacts, characterizing what were called "project cemeteries". This dynamic was understood to result from a lack of articulation between agendas, the scarcity of perennial financing, and the absence of an integrated strategy.

Despite the difficulties identified, the group ended the round with a constructive perspective. It was recognized that the workshop represented a powerful moment of listening, exchange, and joint construction of ideas. The discussions generated between the participants, the shared learnings, and the clarity on the challenges form a solid basis for future actions. Sharing responsibilities, coordinating strategies, and strengthening mutual trust were identified as viable and necessary ways to achieve real and sustainable transformations.

Exploring sociobioeconomies and conservation finance from multiple perspectives

The second day of the workshop was dedicated to a set of thematic interviews. The aim was to deepen the collective understanding of Amazonian sociobioeconomies and Conservation Finance from diverse perspectives – NGOs, communities and the private sector – and to promote connections between these fields.

Five rounds of interviews were conducted, divided throughout the day, guided by three main axes:

1. Sociobioeconomies based on the type of organization (NGOs, communities, private sector)
2. Conservation Finance
3. Connections between sociobioeconomies and conservation finance

The event's first round of interviews addressed the topic of sociobioeconomies from the perspective of non-governmental organizations (NGOs). During the interview conducted by Trent Blare, Ecuador's representative at the International Potato Center (CIP/CGIAR), representatives of two NGOs with a strong presence in sociobioeconomy — Paulina Espín from TRIAS (Ecuador) and Carlos Koury from IDESAM (Brazil) — shared experiences, strategies, learnings, and visions for the future of their work in the Amazon and the Andes. The aim was to deepen the understanding of how these organizations promote sustainable and inclusive value chains adapted to the socioenvironmental context in which they operate, with special attention to youth, women, innovation, and scale of impact.

The second round brought the community's perspective. Adevaldo Dias, president of the Chico Mendes Memorial and advisor of ASPROC (Brazil), and Ruth Cayapa, president of the Kallari Association (Ecuador), represented community members who operate directly in their territories, managing resources, and facing the daily impacts of conservation and production. Adevaldo shared ASPROC's experience in the Brazilian Amazon, and Ruth brought the experience of Kallari, an indigenous Kichwa cooperative from Ecuador that works with community cocoa production in a sustainable way.

The third round of interviews featured Andrea Ortiz, director of the Despensa Amazónica (Peru), and Claudio Padua, coordinator of sociobioeconomy at the Institute for Ecological Research (IPÊ/Brazil). This round brought the perspective of those who work at the intersection between sustainable markets and technical-scientific knowledge. Andrea shared how Despensa Amazónica promotes Amazonian products to urban and international markets, based on the appreciation of biocultural diversity. Claudio presented IPÊ's trajectory, its methodological and political contributions to the sociobioeconomy, highlighting the importance of collaborative networks and the training of local leaders.

The fourth round of interviews focused on conservation finance. Claudio Padua interviewed Manoel Serrão, superintendent of FUNBIO (Brazilian Biodiversity Fund), and Marcelo Cwerner, Brazilian and head of capital flow at the Amazon Investor Coalition. Manoel presented FUNBIO's work as an environmental development fund that seeks to fill financing gaps for biodiversity, highlighting the challenges of aligning financial flows with lasting and scalable impacts on territories. Marcelo addressed the role of the Amazon Investors Coalition in the articulation between investors and sustainable projects in the Amazon region.

The fifth and final round of interviews included discussion of what connects sociobioeconomies to Conservation Finance. This panel included David Solano, currently a researcher at the Peruvian University of Applied Sciences (Peru), and Renato Farias, director of Trust Consultoria (Brazil). This last interview offered a more systemic view. David reflected on the points of convergence between community practices and financial instruments, stating that it is necessary to create a common field of language and objectives between these two worlds. Renato emphasized that it is necessary to build bridges between financing and the

values that move communities. He drew attention to the role of consultants in supporting community leaders to structure their projects so that they attract investment without compromising community principles.

Sociobioeconomies from the perspective of non-governmental organizations

Figure 10 Moderator and interviewees of the first plenary of interviews.

Interviewees: Paulina Espin (TRIAS/Ecuador) and Carlos Koury (IDESAM/Brazil)

Paulina Espin began by sharing that, although the term "sociobioeconomy" is recent in terms of nomenclature, the practices that compose it have been implemented for years. The TRIAS organization works mainly with the cocoa chain, promoting inclusive and resilient agriculture in the face of climate change.

An essential point of the organization's work is the inclusion of young people and women in the agricultural sector through a specific methodology focused on gender and youth. This starts with territorial diagnoses and culminates in action plans for the training and professionalization of these groups.

She explained that young people and women face specific obstacles, such as lack of access to land or financing, and therefore, the work ranges from training in leadership and marketing to promoting entrepreneurship in the value chain. As a result, groups of young people have emerged who specialize in agricultural services (such as phytosanitary control) and groups of women who develop businesses in gastronomy, providing food to tourists and workers.

The organization collaborates with producer associations, which consider themselves members of TRIAS whose role is to strengthen these organizations to make them more autonomous and resilient, both economically and institutionally. This includes everything from improving governance to developing their own companies to support marketing and negotiation of fair prices.

Figure 11 Participant during a panel presentation with NGO representatives.

Carlos Koury described the trajectory of IDESAM, which in 2024 celebrated 20 years of operation. He divided this trajectory into three phases:

1. Pilot phase – development of local arrangements to demonstrate the feasibility of alternative Sociobioeconomy models and to influence public policy.
2. Implementation phase – transformation of pilot experiences into structured projects, with a focus on inclusion and community replicability, prioritizing inclusive territorial agreements.
3. Expansion and scalability phase – consolidation of sustainable businesses in Amazonian production chains, such as agroforestry, coffee and vegetable oils, while also articulating an agenda of innovation and business acceleration.

IDESAM's objective is to promote sustainable businesses based on forest assets and local communities. One of the most emblematic examples presented by Carlos Koury was the process of developing coffee production within an agroforestry system. Initially, coffee production was used as a strategy for the recovery of degraded areas, promoting both environmental and economic benefits. The model consisted of implementing agroforestry systems with native and productive species, while coffee held up the flagship axis. This model evolved into the production of organic coffee and, later, premium organic coffee, serving the most demanding markets with the highest added value.

This process involved:

- Training of producers to adopt agroecological techniques.
- Ongoing technical support from IDESAM.
- Creation of minimum infrastructure for drying and processing.
- Certification strategies and brand positioning.

- Alliances with conscientious buyers interested in sustainable chains.

Another highlight was Inatu, a collective brand and marketing model of plant-based oils from the Amazon. Initially, communities involved competed with each other for market space. With the support of IDESAM, a single brand was created, Inatu, which consolidated producers under a common identity, allowing quality standardization, larger volumes offered, and greater visibility and negotiation power with better market conditions. Inatu works with:

- Extraction of plant-based oils from species such as andiroba, copaiba and pracaxi.
- Shared laboratories for extraction and processing.
- Collective marketing strategies.
- Participation in marketing fairs and digital platforms.
- Technical assistance and certifications to access niche markets.

According to Carlos, this type of horizontal and multilateral arrangement (horizontalization of scale), in which multiple actors participate in production and services (from the producer to the processor to product designers and sales specialists) has been more effective than verticalized models focused on a single actor. According to him, "*diversification gives more results than verticalization.*" Instruments such as shared production spaces and acceleration vehicles are key pieces in this process. For example, in an açaí business, in addition to the producer, those who manufacture equipment, process, transport, certify, etc., come into play. This diversification of actors and functions strengthens the local economy, creates more opportunities, and makes systems more resilient.

During the interview, Carlos Koury stressed that, in the innovation agenda within the sociobioeconomy, IDESAM's focus has been to identify technical solutions or production processes that have already been developed but have not yet reached the market. One example cited was the creation of a machine for harvesting açaí, which removes the producer from the high physical risk associated with climbing slender açaí palms for fruit harvest. The technology had already been researched by scientific and technological institutions, but the business model did not yet exist. A student from Roraima developed a functional harvest prototype. IDESAM brought that prototype to material fruition and supported its entry into the market.

Another crucial variable pointed out was the legal and institutional environment of the territories. The successful cases that IDESAM presented were invariably in areas with legal certainty, and clear territorial planning and licensing capacity. These are territories that already have planning compatible with sustainable use, in addition to existing and operational public policies.

Carlos warned of the need not to reinvent the wheel: many instruments already exist (such as rural credit, technical assistance, public policies), but they do not reach the communities due to failures in implementation, the absence of mediating agents, and the distance between policy design and countryside realities.

It is in this network architecture, with business acceleration vehicles, shared production spaces, and favorable regulatory frameworks, that he sees the most promising path for the sustainable development of the Amazon.

Financing and economic sustainability

In terms of financing, the interviewees presented different but convergent models in the search for sustainability and local autonomy. Paulina explained that the TRIAS model is based on cooperation with producer organizations that are considered partners in the development process. Funding comes from projects focused on conservation and inclusion (gender and youth), funded by government agencies and European donors. One key difference is a continuous investment in training managers and technicians to negotiate fair prices and certifications, which improves financial return.

Figure 12 Participants during the presentation on the panel with NGO representatives.

Paulina reported that, after about 6 to 7 years of TRIAS support, 70-80% of these cooperatives reached their break-even point. Progress observed includes strengthening governance and member services. However, new challenges arise, such as European regulations that require formalization of traditionally informal products.

At IDESAM, funding started with philanthropy and today is moving towards a *blended finance model*, or hybrid finance. This includes philanthropic capital (to correct initial asymmetries), working capital, and innovation and acceleration instruments with social returns.

An important highlight is the capture of financial resources stemming from the legal obligation of companies in the Manaus Free Trade Zone to invest in R & D (Research and Development). Although these resources were previously concentrated in Manaus Free Trade Zone structures, these resources are now being decentralized with active IDESAM intervention. Under IDESAM guidance, a public call for proposals was created, which led to a redistribution of these resources to small businesses, benefiting 80 initiatives so far. In addition, they are currently working with two accelerators — ImpactBank and ForestFee — that offer micro-investments with returns for investors, a promising model of fintechs with impact.

Carlos also highlighted the concern to respect the diversity of Amazonian actors: IDESAM created a specific call for RD&I (Research, Development & Innovation) proposals to support indigenous entrepreneurship, especially Indigenous peoples with master's and doctoral degrees, promoting the application of their knowledge to favor their own territories.

Challenges and strategies to overcome

The main challenges facing TRIAS initiatives include:

- Instability of product prices;
- Difficulty of true inclusion of young people, many without access to land or credit;
- Impacts of climate change, which introduce new pests and force farmers to rethink crop choices and planting options.

He notes that engaging young people from an early age is critical, and that technical and financial support should be considered with their realities in mind.

Carlos pointed out that "everything is difficult" and that even solutions such as agroforestry are not immune to climate effects, where the climate can change abruptly and compromise all production. The scalability of initiatives is often hampered by the absence of infrastructure, credit, and effective public policies. However, as anchors of hope, he highlighted the strength of communities, a growing interest from academia, and the work of people willing to make a difference.

Questions & Answers

During this session, the workshop took on a tone of recognition and thoughtful provocation, highlighting both the challenges faced by civil society organizations and possible ways to strengthen the Amazonian sociobioeconomy. The conversation began with a gesture of gratitude to those present, recognizing the daily work carried out in adverse contexts, with few resources and the need for constant adjustments, different from the margin of error tolerated in the private sector.

The exchanges were deepened with practical questions on the organizational models within communities and associations. Ways in which some organizations work to strengthen existing cooperatives and associations was shared, providing tools for risk analysis and improving internal processes. In these experiences, payments to producers are defined based on the real costs of production, added to fair premiums that return to the organizational structures themselves, reinforcing local autonomy and sustainability.

The reflections were also directed to the future. The workshop projected, in an exercise of collective imagination, what is expected of the Amazonian economies fifty years from now. The emerging vision was that of a forest-rooted economy, where financial instruments would be secured by forest assets and the value added of Amazonian products would be transferred within the Amazon itself. The current economic model frequently was criticized, in which the processing of products, such as açaí, is mostly done outside the region, resulting in a loss of local value and opportunities. This debate reinforced the idea that changing the logic of consumption and extractivism is a fundamental step towards reversing the current destructive model. Small collective actions, guided by this vision, were pointed out as the way to build this transformation incrementally and sustainably.

The discussion advanced towards a critical analysis of the domain of the productive system. One point of consensus was that there is still much to understand. Learning is continuous and problems evolve along with the maturation of production chains. The audacity and bold actions needed to unlock the full potential of these chains has yet to be reached, both in terms of financial resources and coordinated development strategies. Instead of ambitious structuring of production chains, many initiatives have adapted to the limited available financing, slowing the escalation to more advanced levels.

Another important axis of debate was the disconnect between rural areas and city centers. The workshop addressed the challenges of engaging the urban public, which concentrates the majority of consumers and has the power of choice in the market. Experiences such as "rural vacations" and organized visits to communities were shared, as well as certification strategies that bring consumers closer to the values of agroecology and sustainable production. These actions seek to translate, for the urban population, the positive impacts of sustainable livelihoods and forest-based production.

The importance of partnerships with companies and digital platforms was also addressed. Some successful experiences include collaboration with brands and companies that value the sociobioeconomy, as well as festivals and events that connect producers, investors, and researchers (such as Fiinsa). Another example cited was the use of markets with sectors dedicated to products with positive impact, which has provided logistical conditions and expanded visibility for Amazonian producers.

The first round of interviews brought to light concrete practices, lessons learned, and the complexity of doing sociobioeconomy in the territory. The experiences of TRIAS and IDESAM reinforce the importance of:

- Inclusive models adapted to local contexts;
- Smart and diversified financing;
- Connection with urban consumers and coherent public policies;
- And above all, resilience and hope in the collective.

As Paulina said, quoting Galeano: *"Little people doing small things in small places can change the world."*

Sociobioeconomies from the perspective of communities

The second round of interviews was dedicated to community experiences in sociobioeconomy. The interview, conducted by Claudio Padua, sought to understand the journey of community organizations in strengthening local sociobioeconomies, their articulation with markets, the construction of sustainable business agreements, and the essential link between conservation and income generation.

Adevaldo Dias, from the Chico Mendes Memorial and advisor to ASPROC (Association of Rural Producers of Carauari), shared the trajectory of of this Amazonian organization that began in the 1990s. Ruth Cayapa, president of the Kallari Association in Ecuador, presented a 20-year journey in community organizations with the aim of strengthening a quality cocoa chain, which today produces chocolates with national and international recognition.

ASPROC Experience

Adevaldo began his story by recalling the origins of ASPROC, an organization with more than 30 years of experience in Carauari, a municipality in the interior of the Amazon, seven days by boat from the state capital of Manaus. ASPROC was born as a response to a structural crisis: the collapse of the rubber economy and the need for survival of local populations who began to migrate towards family farming practices in a context of extreme isolation and inequality.

The turning point began with popular education promoted by the Catholic Church, inspired by the Paulo Freire method. According to Adevaldo, this awareness-raising process led residents to understand the exploitation they suffered at the hands of the "owners of the territories," which triggered a mobilization for autonomy and territorial organization. ASPROC began to act broadly, from political articulation for the formal recognition of their inhabited territories to the implementation of sustainable productive management.

The mobilization to create their own alternatives resulted in the creation of the first Federal Sustainable Development Reserve (RDS) in Amazonas and an Extractive Reserve (RESEX). Within this new institutional framework, community management of pirarucu was developed.

Figure 13 Participant during the panel presentation with community representatives.

Adevaldo explained that, as it is a species with strong fishing control, it can only be exploited on indigenous lands, sustainable development reserves, and areas with fishing agreements. Thus, the communities began a rigorous monitoring of the populations and, with IBAMA authorization, began to manage up to 30% of the adults, maintaining conservation as the central pillar of production.

Instead of selling fresh fish, as was done before, they started processing it, freezing it and adding value. Adevaldo pointed out that ASPROC's success comes from three pillars: a solid community organization, the ability to add value to the product, and strategic political advocacy. A striking case was the transformation of an intermediary's default payment into an opportunity: a businessman who did not pay for a load of pirarucu led ASPROC to demand compensation in the form of services. The debtor's slaughterhouse began to process the community's fish, offering services that included fish freezing and returning the processed fish ready for sale.

This new product presentation opened doors to sales in more demanding and distant markets, conquered markets in the Brazilian Southeast and Midwest, and even exported to Asia. The association now has working capital, and this agreement allowed for a 50% increase in executive compensation compared to the conventional market.

According to Adevaldo, the impact of ASPROC's entry into the pirarucu market was direct: the price paid to the fisherman rose from R\$ 6 to R\$ 10, an increase motivated not only by organizational logistics, but also by the recognition of a quality product and conservation effort. Currently, ASPROC supports seven other community organizations, replicating this model.

Kallari's Experience

Ruth in turn, told the story of the Kallari organization, born in the early 2000s from the arrival of an international volunteer to a community near a reserve in Ecuador. Initially involved in handicrafts with local seeds, women in the community faced difficulties in accessing markets outside the community. Over time, the opportunity arose to add value to local production through cocoa.

Ten communities came together to organize the cocoa chain, which involved between 50 and 60 producers, "*strengthening what already existed and seeking technical assistance to move forward.*" The organization has structured a chain based on community strengthening, technical assistance, collective storage, and local processing.

With the increase in cocoa quality and product acceptance, a desire to go further arose. The organization's progress has culminated in the production of high-quality chocolates with national and international recognition. "*We have 13 flavors of chocolate with national acceptance and even export. The factory produces, but we are the ones who have the income and earn from cacao.*"

Figure 14 Participant presenting a product produced by his association.

Ruth pointed out that, in addition to production, the cultivation system, known as the "chakra system", typical of the Quechua peoples, is an ancestral model of agroforestry, where cocoa, food species such as bananas and cassava, and ancestral knowledge coexist. *"Chakra is a living school for our children. It is where we teach to conserve, to take care of the land, to respect the forest."*

The challenges and strategies

Adevaldo spoke about geographical isolation, low prices in local markets and corruption in public procurement processes, such as the PNAE (National School Feeding Program). *"To get on the shopping list, they asked for bribes. Corruption is very great,"* he lamented. With the support of a project supported by the American Forest Service, they invested in marketing and reinforced alternative sales channels to compete with the illegality of the local market, and began selling to the southeast and midwest of Brazil, and have already exported to Asia.

Ruth reinforced the importance of diversifying production and income sources, with the local marketing of other products in the periods between cocoa harvests. The chakra system, with *"about 500 plants associated with other species,"* allows for production of alternative crops for marketing and for local consumption so that families have permanent access to local commerce.

Questions & Answers

One of the main topics discussed was market positioning and the construction of perceived value in the products of Sociobioeconomy chains. The discussion revolved around the challenge of combining conservation and market competitiveness, especially in the context of traditional and community products.

The initial provocation arose with the question of how to build a clear and communicable difference for the consumer, in order to increase the perceived value of products. The collective reflection recognized that, in addition to the intrinsic quality of products, it is necessary to invest in marketing, traceability, and transparency. A practical example presented at the workshop highlighted the importance of developing localized communication tools: a community committed to the creation of a website and the training of a person from the region itself to oversee institutional communication, strengthening the link between product origin and the consumer. This communication effort seeks to show how the products are made and what values sustain them, such as justice, collective work, environmental conservation, and respect for local culture.

The conversation also highlighted a central tension: the true cost of conservation is rarely recognized in the final price. It was revealed that in some production chains, up to 40% of the cost of the product is directly related to environmental preservation due to necessary monitoring, surveillance, and protection of ecosystems.

However, this community conservation effort is often not fairly remunerated. Even when the consumer recognizes the added value, there is a socially acceptable price ceiling, which limits the internalization of these costs. The reflection at the workshop highlighted the paradox between symbolic valuation and actual payment, noting that if communities were remunerated in the same way that the state spends to protect a conservation unit, there would be less need to harvest resources such as pirarucu. According to one participant, *"If the community received the same payment that the public service spends to protect a conservation unit, we wouldn't even need to capture pirarucu."*

The discussion evolved towards sources of financing and institutional support. Participants shared experiences of access to cooperative international and national technical resources, including agencies such as FAO, GIZ, TRIAS, and the Pachamama Foundation. It was stressed that, even when there are internal disagreements about accepting this type of support, the collective governance of the organizations defines the priorities and the funds are allocated to productive strengthening and economic sustainability.

The legal and symbolic recognition of sustainable production systems was also discussed. A concrete example demonstrated how initiatives have sought certifications that validate their production systems for even international markets, affirming that their production chains conserve forests and provide socioenvironmental value. These certifications are considered strategic tools to open markets and legitimize the work of communities before the urban, national, and international consumer publics.

The experiences shared by Adevaldo and Ruth demonstrate the complexity and strength of community initiatives in the context of sociobioeconomies. Both demonstrated how local organization, combined with well-planned strategies for sustainable management and insertion into differentiated markets, can generate significant impacts in isolated and often underserved territories.

Both cases face persistent challenges, such as access to markets, poor infrastructure, high conservation costs, and in some cases, uneven institutional practices. However, their responses to these challenges have been strategically formulated through alliances with different partners, professionalization of production, and development of marketing networks based on transparency and traceability.

These experiences reinforce that community-based solutions can be robust and adaptable, especially when the central role of local populations in managing their territories is formally recognized.

Practices and challenges in the construction of an Amazonian sociobioeconomy

In this round of interviews, conducted by Trent Blare, the guests shared in detail concrete experiences, strategic visions, and critical reflections on the construction of initiatives related to the sociobioeconomy in the Amazon. The dialogue between Andrea Ortiz, director of Despensa Amazónica (Peru), and Claudio Padua, director of Sociobioeconomy at IPÊ (Brazil), highlighted the operational subtleties, structural challenges and tensions between community innovation and conventional market dynamics. The conversations highlighted the role of sustainable production chains, the centrality of biodiversity as an asset for development, and the importance of social inclusion, especially of women, in the production process.

Initiatives and context

Andrea Ortiz began her story by telling how it all started from a collaboration with a childhood friend, a chef who has worked in New York and Italy. After international experiences, he returned to Peru and was confronted with the fact that the country's haute cuisine was deeply influenced by European traditions. During his visit to the markets of Iquitos and Loreto, he discovered a great diversity of Amazonian products little used by the national cuisine. Thus began a years-long immersion in university research, seeking to better understand this diversity of products that are not valued in high-end restaurants.

Figure 15 Participant during a panel with representatives of the private sector.

It was in this context that Andrea, with a background in business management, came in to help him initially structure an academic presentation. The joint work evolved into something bigger: a concrete proposal to structure a value chain that would allow the sustainable use of these Amazonian products in gastronomy. The big challenge, she explained, was to ensure food security, regularity of supply, and sustainability. "*The chain was very complex, the slaughterhouses were insufficient, and the quality and standardization varied greatly,*" she said. They began to intuitively solve logistical and structural bottlenecks, developing a research-based methodology to identify products with gastronomic potential in each community. They identified gaps, such as a lack of training, infrastructure, and logistics, and began to address them to connect communities to the market.

This approach involved three fronts: production organization, transport logistics, and marketing strategies. At first, the chef's restaurant bought almost all of the production. Later, they expanded marketing channels, even out of necessity during the pandemic.

In addition to the restaurant, two projects stood out: one with pirarucu, in which they worked adding value with specific cuts, patties, and nuggets; and another with the promotion and marketing of local products with gastronomic potential. The initiative began to organize the entire process, from ingredient research in the field to training, infrastructure (such as slaughterhouses), marketing, and branding.

Cláudio Padua, in turn, provided a conceptual reflection. He talked about two MIT papers that compared economic development to a LEGO game, where you have to combine existing pieces to create something new. "*Our big LEGO box is Amazonian biodiversity,*" he said. However, this "box" is locked and only opened occasionally. And the key to opening it up is knowledge. Cláudio argued that the combination of research, development, and entrepreneurship is essential to create nature-based solutions.

Figure 16 Participant during a panel with representatives of the private sector.

Based on this vision, Cláudio has articulated a network of Amazonian entrepreneurs through IPÊ, offering tools such as marketing, branding and access to markets. For him, trust within the community is a fundamental capital to enable real change. According to Claudio, "*there is no shortage of entrepreneurs in the Amazon. What they lack are the tools and ecosystem needed to thrive.*" He emphasized the role of trust within communities, something that can only be achieved through genuine participation in local processes.

Inclusion and local transformations

Andrea recounted an illustrative situation about gender and power: when they set up an ice factory to ensure the preservation of fish, they realized that the entire local economy was dominated by men. They then proposed that the factory be managed by women from the community. "*At first, men accepted it. But now they want to reclaim the land where the factory is located,*" she said. The men did not like women's economic independence. This has led to conflicts, and the team is looking for negotiated solutions.

Andrea also reported the development of a caviar made of *carachama* (a species of Amazonian catfish), accompanied by gastronomic research, prototyping, and branding. She emphasized that the work requires acting on three points: making production viable, solving logistics, and promoting product communication.

In addition, she pointed out that there is a huge regulatory vacuum in Peru. Fisheries legislation only contemplates marine fishing, and the authorities of Lima, far from the Amazonian reality, do not recognize local specificities. "*We are trying to bring about regulatory changes. Each*

product brings something new, but the sanitary requirements are designed for large sea chains, not for artisanal production in rivers."

Greenwashing and value capture

Claudio Padua warned about the risks of large corporations capturing environmental agendas. According to him, there is a tendency for companies to appropriate sustainable narratives without effectively changing their practices. He argues that it is necessary to create mechanisms to separate legitimate practices from *greenwashing*.

Claudio also shared his career as a serial entrepreneur, seeking to create companies that, in addition to profit, generate a positive impact. *"There is no magic formula to change behavior, but money changes behavior. If you earn more by doing well, you change."* But for him, there is a fear that even spectacular entrepreneurial experiences will not be sufficiently significant, so that desired, less environmentally damaging companies can grow and compete with the soy economy, for example.

Andrea complemented this idea by saying that conventional and socioeconomic businesses can and should coexist. She pointed out that conventional companies have a very defined *"end result"*, that is, a logic of profits that will hardly be abandoned. But that doesn't mean they should be dismissed or attacked. On the contrary, she defended the commitment to these companies, not as adversaries, but as strategic allies, either as buyers or partners in consulting processes.

Working with the corporate sector, she says, requires a kind of pedagogical work: *"It's important to sermonize within these companies."* The choice of the term is not accidental: it is a matter of bringing new criteria, values, and worldviews to environments that still work with other logics. According to Andrea, there is a willingness to listen within large corporations, even if the starting points are different.

Thus, she defended a non-dichotomous approach: *"It is necessary to transform logic, not as extremes. It is necessary to coordinate within the existing logic to generate real changes."* For Andrea, the transformation must be organic, built from what already exists, even if it requires adaptations. And she concludes with a clear warning: *"It is naïve to think that the sociobioeconomy will be the master of capitalism."*

Claudio Padua complemented with a pragmatic and direct vision: the entry point for any transformation within companies is the top of the hierarchy. For him, any attempt at transformation that only goes through the intermediate or operational levels tends to fail, because there is a strong hierarchy within companies. *"You have to talk to the owner, the one in charge."* His speech clearly exposed the power dynamics in large corporate structures and the need for strategic approaches.

Questions & Answers

One of the first points raised by the plenary group was the need to escape from the Manichean logic that separates the world between destructive companies and those considered saviors of biodiversity. The discussion highlighted the complexity of the greenwashing phenomenon, revealing that not every corporate narrative about sustainability is necessarily false or mere

advertising. It was pointed out that there are important nuances between the narrative, the brand strategy, and the real commitment to socioenvironmental transformation. Recognizing these layers is essential to avoid falling into simplistic judgments and, at the same time, not allowing oneself to be co-opted by empty discourses.

Another axis of the discussion focused on the tension between community and business logic. It was pointed out directly, that *"working with companies is a matter of profit. For communities, it's about livelihoods and ways of life."* This phrase points to one of the asymmetries in the field of sociobioeconomy: the divergence of motivations between the actors in the chain. The workshop recognized that while for many, the economy is an instrument of subsistence and maintenance of livelihoods, for others it is a space for expansion and maximization of financial results. These realities are often not on the same plane.

The discussion evolved into an analysis of the internal transformations in the communities. There was a shared perception that the traditional figure of the community leader has been losing space, especially in contexts where power arrangements have become more hybrid and diverse. The concrete experience of a fishing community was presented as an example: there, indigenous women assumed the leadership of an ice factory, initially supported by all. However, women's economic autonomy began to generate discomfort and conflicts. The case illustrates the dilemmas and advances of the real processes of change: *"They need the ice. And now they have to get it from women. And they don't like it."*

The workshop also addressed the relationship with the private sector from a strategic point of view. The sociobioeconomy field was criticized for continuing to understand little about the functioning and challenges faced by large industries. It was stressed that it is a mistake to maintain a direct confrontational relationship with this sector without understanding its internal pressures, such as deadlines, bureaucracies, regulatory requirements, and the logic of scale. In this sense, the proposal that was discussed was to act more proactively: prepare the territories in advance, invest in planning and building capacity, so that when companies look for sustainable solutions, they find robust and well-structured systems. With this strategy, it would be possible to move away from the reactive position and establish more balanced negotiations, based on the concrete offer of viable alternatives to the traditional extractive logic.

Conservation Finance

The first panel in the afternoon delved into financing applied to conservation and sociobioeconomy, focusing on the financial mechanisms available, the limitations of existing models, and opportunities to develop new approaches capable of valuing the socioenvironmental assets of the Amazon and other biodiverse territories. Led by Claudio Padua, the conversation brought with it the technical and practical vision of Marcelo Cwerner, Head of Capital Flow at Amazon Investor Coalition, and Manoel Serrão, Superintendent of FUNBIO – Brazilian Fund for Biodiversity.

Conscious financing

Marcelo began his participation by offering a broad perspective, built from his professional career on different fronts of impact financing. He introduced the concept of "continuous capital," or *multi-capital*, a logic that recognizes that each stage of a business's development

requires different financing profiles, especially when it comes to businesses focused on conservation and nature.

In the conventional business model, Marcelo explained, the initial capital usually comes from its own sources: the entrepreneur himself, his/her family, or business partners. But in the context of community-based or environmentally-based businesses, this start-up capital is scarce or nonexistent. *"That's where philanthropy comes in,"* he said. Philanthropy plays, according to him, a fundamental role in creating conditions for start-ups to emerge.

Marcelo highlighted the work of the Amazon Investor Coalition, which makes modest initial contributions (up to R\$ 500,000), but accompanied by strategic support and network connections, which strengthen entrepreneurs in multiple dimensions. This support goes beyond the financial and aims to build, together with the entrepreneur, a sustainable path.

As companies mature, they access other layers of capital, including reimbursable philanthropic capital, which serves as a bridge to trade financing. *"Impact companies need financial creativity,"* he said. And for this to work, a deeper dialogue between investors and investees is needed, with a new mindset of collaboration.

For Marcelo, the growth of the sociobioeconomy and the Conservation Finance depend on the creation of greater environmental awareness among all the entities involved, including society as a whole. He ended his discourse with a historical and ethical provocation: *"Just as slave labor was a market logic in the past, the current logic that ignores the socioenvironmental component will also become obsolete. ESG and impact companies are still timid steps in the face of what we need, but they are the right steps and should be adopted faster."*

Diversity of funds, risks, and the challenge of modernizing the financial architecture

Next, Manoel Serrão provided the institutional vision of someone who has been working in the management of complex funds for decades. He described FUNBIO's financial architecture, highlighting the multiplicity of funds and sources, from GEF (Global Environment Facility) resources to private funds created from environmental offsets.

Manoel detailed the three pillars that support the funds managed by FUNBIO:

1. **Volume:** Scale and amount of resources available.
2. **Flexibility:** Many resources are linked to constraints (such as exclusive use in conservation units), which limits the response to local realities.
3. **Accessibility:** This refers to the transaction costs and complexity of accessing funds, which often require time, extensive documentation, and a high reputational cost.

Figure 17 Participant during the presentation

He gave the example of the case of Rio de Janeiro, where the oil industry had R\$ 300 million in environmental compensation that it could not execute. FUNBIO created a private fund with public governance, which allowed it to unlock those resources. Today, 35% of the total managed by FUNBIO comes from private obligations, such as Terms of Adjustment of Conduct (TACs), fines, and conversions of environmental sanctions.

However, Serrão warned that the current model is aged. *"We are still with the same vehicle, but the world has changed,"* he said. He cited factors such as the hollowing out of multilateralism during the Trump administration, the effects of wars, and the migration crises, which have displaced international donor priorities.

The way out, he says, is in the search for *blended financing* — models that combine reimbursable funds with philanthropy and financial institution partnerships. *"We are collaborating with banks. Not to be responsible for the reimbursable part, but as proponents."*

Serrão acknowledged that there are failures, obstacles, and constant learning, but reinforced the need for innovation and resilience: *"If we don't pay attention to the aging of systems, we will suffer."*

Claudio Padua asks: *"Are we prepared for this shift from conventional economics to sociobioeconomies? Do financial agents think differently?"* According to Marcelo, many investors are still stuck in conventional logic. However, there are growing efforts, such as the ones he follows, to create methodologies that value the positive externalities of the sociobioeconomy. He exemplified the management of pirarucu, the production of Brazil nuts and açaí, all activities that generate positive impacts, such as the surveillance, conservation and maintenance of the standing forest, but which are not monetized. The market only looks at the final product, ignoring the value of the associated ecosystem services.

Figure 18 Participant during a panel presentation with conservation finance experts.

"Negative externalities are already monetized with fines. But the positives have not yet translated into economic value." For Marcelo, when it is possible to incorporate these intangible assets (biodiversity, water cycle, soil vitality) into the accounting and financial logic, the sociobioeconomy will gain another scale. He mentioned biodiversity credits and PES (Payment for Environmental Services) mechanisms as promising, but still nascent initiatives.

Manoel complemented with a realistic view of the limits of these mechanisms. He mentioned the REDD Early Movers program, which makes payments for results, but which reaches the State as an independent resource, that is, it can be spent without a direct link to conservation,

as in the case of Mato Grosso, which invests in family farming and indigenous communities, but does not include conservation units.

According to him, REDD remunerates the flow, but not the biodiversity stock, which can distort incentives and make the instrument even more "perverse". He also cited *green bonds*, which account for a very small fraction of bank profits, saying, "Global investments are large, but they don't mobilize enough resources to bring about a transformation."

Questions & Answers

The session began with the provocative question — whether the advance of the voluntary carbon market would be negatively affecting philanthropy — the group explored the different functions and action-oriented moments of each type of capital. Participants recognized that philanthropy plays a crucial role in the early stages of projects, when risks are high and business models are not yet mature. At this time, it acts as a "brave" capital, which sustains the structuring phase and tolerates conditions that do not yet arouse market interest. As projects move forward, become self-sustaining, or enter markets such as carbon, it is desirable that philanthropy withdraws, freeing up space for other forms of financing. In this sense, the transition of funding sources would be a sign of the project's maturity.

"Philanthropy enters when there is nothing operational yet. It is capital that can take on more risk, that sustains the initial phase, to which no one else wants to venture. It works like the 'glue', when the risks outweigh the benefits. But once the project is structured and finds a way to sustain itself financially, as is the case with many forest restoration projects through the voluntary carbon market, philanthropy must leave the scene," said the participant, an expert in Conservation Finance.

The group also brought more critical and institutional views on this logic. It was recalled that the behavior of international philanthropy does not always *only* respond to the initial stage of project development, but also to political factors, such as the context of the federal government. Landmark cases were cited to demonstrate that philanthropy returns en masse under certain contexts, even without clear guidelines for action. *"In the Bolsonaro government there was a strong retreat from international philanthropy. In Lula's government, it came back in large volume, but without a clear direction from the government,"* commented one participant.

In addition, not all investments in socioenvironmental projects respond directly to market dynamics. There are reputational motivations, legal obligations, or attempts to compensate for environmental responsibilities. The Floresta Viva project, carried out with BNDES, was cited as an example, where the motivation for voluntary contributions was varied, not always directly related to the carbon market, but also due to legal obligations and reputational commitments. This is the case of Belo Monte, which attracted resources due to its socioenvironmental responsibilities.

The consensus of the workshop was that philanthropy remains essential to create *enabling conditions* such as community banks, adapted funds, and technical capacity building, especially in territories with little access to conventional credit.

Another point discussed was the relationship between NDCs (Nationally Determined Contributions) and the release of multilateral bank funds. Participants expressed scepticism about the effectiveness of these international commitments as financing instruments. Most countries have not met the previous targets, and there is little prospect that the current ones will

serve as a trigger for significant financial flows. Participant criticisms focused on the fact that multilateral banks should act more autonomously and proactively, creating lines of financing directly linked to community and conservation projects, without depending on the agenda of national governments. At the same time, some participants emphasized the political value of COPs as spaces for negotiation, albeit linked to slow transformation. Others were more pragmatic, betting on strengthening bilateralism with countries such as Norway, Germany, and England as the most effective strategy to attract concrete resources.

An important axis of the conversation addressed the limits and opportunities of financing not only the products of the sociobioeconomy, but the entire market structure and associated ecosystem services. The group reflected on the difficulty of transforming positive impacts such as the conservation of a forest into tangible financial assets, while negative impacts remain externalities at no additional cost. It was discussed how biological assets could be incorporated into the *valuation* of companies, especially when they do not generate direct cash flow, as in the case of standing forests. Some practical examples were shared, such as the initiative to finance suppliers in the açai chain, where capital is advanced with guarantees from the buyer, creating a structure that strengthens the chain without requiring advance payment.

In the area of Payments for Environmental Services (PES), the workshop recognized that, although it is a well-established concept, there is still a gap between theoretical recognition and effective remuneration. Many previous experiments, such as the attempt to assign a Total Economic Value (VET) to ecosystems, have failed due to a lack of practical payment mechanisms. In this sense, environmental services will only have a real value when there is a willingness to remunerate them.

To close the debate, the absence of the insurance sector in the discussions on sociobioeconomy financing was pointed out. Given the high degree of risk of these projects, from climatic variations to political and economic instabilities, insurance could play a strategic role in reducing risk perceptions and thus attracting investors who are currently reluctant. The group concluded that it is necessary to broaden the vision of the financial ecosystem and seek more sophisticated articulations, ranging from credit and philanthropy to insurance and new pricing mechanisms for positive externalities. The sociobioeconomy, in this scenario, requires creative financial engineering to recognize the value of those who conserve ecosystems and biodiversity.

Bringing together conservation finance and sociobioeconomy

The conversation led by Pilar Useche, a professor at the University of Florida, brought together David Solano, a researcher at the Peruvian University of Applied Sciences, and Renato Farías, director of Trust Consultoria in Brazil. The aim was to shed light on the challenges and opportunities of combining environmental Conservation Finance with promotion of the sociobioeconomy, especially in the Amazon region. The conversation was enriched by several plenary participants and provided critical perspectives, practical reflections, and experiences in the field.

Pilar opened the session by asking: *"What relationships did we see between the experiences that unite these two themes?"* Renato responded candidly, recalling the times when the institutional focus was on REDD (Reducing Emissions from Deforestation and Forest Degradation), highlighting that although it was a powerful movement, it was also a source of

frustration. Projects that appeared to be institutionally successful proved to be disconnected from local reality over time, revealing structural failures to sustain impacts.

He drew attention to the distance between the private sector's transformative will and its limited understanding of territorial realities. *"The private sector seems to want to do something, but it doesn't understand what's going on. There is a gap between the effectiveness needed for the sociobioeconomy and the desire of the private sector,"* he said. For him, committed people must be bridges that connect intentions and realities. *"The resource transforms, but deep understanding transforms even more."*

David complemented by highlighting the need to operationalize ideas. He shared that he identified *26 essential issues* for this type of coordination, reinforcing the complexity and breadth of the challenges. A practical example was his proposal to integrate sociobiodiverse production into school food programs, the structure of which could dialogue with local production arrangements.

He gave a direct warning: *"For biodiversity to be profitable, it must enter price markets, not just quality markets. We must stop working only with what we know and seek the exchange between experiences. Complexity is not an impediment, it is an invitation to continuous work."*

Pilar's next question was whether the funding sources used recognized local knowledge. Antonio Loboguerrero, involved in funds focused on governance in the Amazon, pointed out that there is greater flexibility in international cooperation funds, especially European, that respect local knowledge and organizational autonomy. On the other hand, private companies in Colombia, for example, showed less openness and tended to impose guidelines.

It provoked reflection: *"What is success really? Is it to take advantage of the market or to solve a specific problem of the community?"* He insisted that success must be seen from the perspective of communities and that funders must broaden their conception of results.

Renato agreed and stressed that short-term projects of 3 to 5 years are not enough to bring about structural changes. For him, real success lies in keeping society active and allowing community organizations to survive and continue to operate after projects end. Flexibility, according to him, is key: *"You have to look at the territory and understand its emergencies, which change over time. The indicators also change."*

Florian Breyer brought up the issue of trust and suggested mechanisms that motivate more proximate investor participation, such as direct experience in the territories where they invest. She proposed a more human connection, suggesting that *"the investor's family spend a week at the locale they funded."*

David cautioned against confusion between *intermediate indicators* and *impact indicators*. He pointed out that many projects focus on easy-to-collect figures – such as visits to fairs – without measuring real changes, such as the strengthening of social groups, economic sustainability, or the improvement of local education. *"Impact evaluation needs stability in the inflow of resources and focus on clear objectives. Sociobioeconomy should also define between three and five minimum characteristics that should occur."*

Pilar reinforced the importance of this distinction, stressing that intermediate indicators do not guarantee the desired final impacts. Paulina questioned the ethical limits of financing: *"What*

to do when the resources come from Amazonian mining or oil companies who are trying to clean up their image?" She defended the need for transparency and traceability.

David shared an emblematic case of *Puerto Maldonado*, where illegal mining generated so much money that those who participated in conservation were viewed with suspicion. The social and moral impact of this financing, even this indirect one, was profound.

Renato noted that, in his experience, his organization rejected resources from sources that could not be publicly disclosed — mining companies, tobacco industries. However, he cautioned that this alone is not enough. It is also necessary to observe how resources are used and with whom.

Karen and Manoel reinforced the importance of knowing the origin of the capital and the partners involved. Manoel referred to the practice of "*knowing your customer*" as a trend that should grow in the sector.

Suzana recalled that the failure of a project affects much more than spreadsheets: *"The failure of a project undermines the credibility of the organization in the eyes of the community. Failure means breaking trust."*

Renato was emphatic in criticizing the misallocation of large volumes of philanthropy in organizations with little practical activity. *"A lot of resources go to large NGOs that generate reports, not changes. The resources must be used to structure and strengthen those who are in the territory."* For him, reports do not transform reality.

Pilar proposed a reflection on the impact of broader pressures to quantify nature. Has this changed business priorities or affected people's relationship with nature? Andrea responded with a forceful example: a project with fishermen and *pirarucu* repopulation. The conservation of the ecosystem increased the supply of fish, which was then valued for its history and relationship with the territory, entering the premium gastronomic market. *"They saw in practice that conserving generated income. A kilo of fish is valued five times."*

Antonio cautioned that the search for numbers often ignores the qualitative value that communities perceive. *"People want numbers, but success is felt qualitatively. We can translate it into numbers later, but we can't ignore that dimension."*

Manoel added that in certain contexts, the measurement effort is poorly received. He shared the case of a project that respected Cancun's safeguards and consulted with the community. However, the community did not want to participate and the Federal Ministry of Public Affairs took a position against the project. *"Measuring impact is not always straightforward, and sometimes it is impossible to attribute a direct cost to an impact because there are multiple factors involved."*

The conversation presented an overview of the challenges and possible paths to align environmental conservation with socioeconomic development. Participant conversations reinforced that in addition to indicators and metrics, what matters are relationships of trust, recognition of local complexities, and deep listening to territories. Finance capital needs to find new ways to address these realities, with ethics, flexibility, and a true commitment to transformation.

Closing interviews and transitioning to group discussions

After concluding the interviews and following a break, Karen Kainer drew from the discussions, discourses, and examples shared in the interviews, highlighting a list of the main themes and challenges of sociobioeconomies and Conservation Finance. Participants were divided into mixed working groups, with people from different countries and sectors, to broaden the exchange of experiences. Groups were invited to discuss and identify:

- **Internal challenges:** factors related to communities and their organizational structures, such as local governance, production, marketing, training, succession, among others.
- **External challenges:** factors beyond the direct control of communities or partner organizations, such as public policies, institutional bureaucracies, market dynamics, climate, infrastructure, among others.

Each group was supported by translators, which allowed everyone to participate effectively, even among people who did not speak the same language. The ideas, reflections, and main points raised were recorded on flip charts intermittently. Presentations of the results of these groups were left for the third day of the workshop.

Scalable, ethical, inclusive, and equitable approaches

The third day of the workshop began with a round of sharing and analysis of the discussions held in groups the previous day. The focus was on the internal and external challenges faced by sociobioeconomies from the perspective of the different actors involved. The reports provided critical reflections, with emphasis on practical experiences in the territories and the obstacles faced in relationships with the financing institutions.

Figure 19 Participants during a group presentation of the challenges for the sociobioeconomy

Group 1: Pilar Useche, Suzana Padua, Manoel Serrão and Vanda Witoto

Internal challenges

The group spoke about the scarcity of resources for indigenous communities and that when they participate, they are often not accompanied by the time needed to establish strong and lasting ties. In the indigenous context, the strengthening of relationships of trust cannot be accelerated or forced. Trust is built with active listening, continuous presence, and respect for community rhythms, something that requires time, dedication, and intercultural sensitivity.

This pattern of intervention, according to the oral reports here, hinders the consolidation of an autonomous and sustainable sociobioeconomy rooted in the territories. It has been reported that projects, especially those implemented by large NGOs, often centralize decisions and resources, creating a dynamic of dependency. When the project cycle ends, there is a lack of continuity, institutional fragility, and a lack of community preparation to manage the processes initiated by themselves. Basic tools are lacking, such as the mastery of accounting, administrative autonomy, and political articulation.

The challenge is to change the logic of external action. Beyond offering quick results or meeting formal objectives, it is necessary to invest in building real capacities with a long-term vision, respect for community times, and commitment to the legacy created after project departure.

External challenges

The discussion extended to aspects external to community governance, focusing especially on the barriers imposed by institutional funders. The group listed the following challenges:

- Inadequate rules and procedures: Institutions such as BNDES and large banks operate with excessively rigid rules, which do not dialogue with the reality of grassroots organizations. On the other hand, it was pointed out that European and North American foundations tend to be more flexible and open to dialogue with local specificities.
- Transaction timelines and costs: Both the time needed to access resources and operational costs (overhead) are relevant challenges. The group's suggestion was that funding should include realistic overheads, on the order of 17–18%, to cover the administrative costs of beneficiary organizations.
- Unrestricted funds: The importance of having unrestricted resources was highlighted, which allows the organization to adapt capitals according to real needs throughout implementation. Funds that are too tied up create inefficiency and reduce the ability to respond to emergency situations.
- Short-term projects: Short deadlines are detrimental to both those who implement them and to funders. One of the solutions pointed out was the combination of resources for different stages as FUNBIO has practiced, which combines philanthropic, public, and reimbursable funds according to the nature of each action. In this model, it is essential that the implementing organization has a minimum structure and a reliable internal organization to ensure funder trust.

Group 2: Karen Kainer, Adevaldo Dias, Marcelo Cwerner and Renato Farias

Internal challenges

One of the central axes identified by this group was the fragility in the management of community enterprises. As one community leader points out, it is often the community members themselves who fully assume administrative functions, without training, technical support, or adequate remuneration. Comparison with conventional companies that have specialized teams in different areas illustrates the asymmetry of community capacity. In community businesses, there is no way to divide tasks when there are not even resources to hire a single person. Management ends up falling to a few, which compromises both efficiency and commitment.

This problem is compounded when considering the challenge of adding value to local production. The absence of minimal physical and technological structure leads communities to operate as suppliers of raw materials, without ability to access the most profitable stages of the production chain. The direct consequence is dependence on intermediaries, low profit margins, and the impossibility of local reinvestment.

Another sensitive point identified was generational succession. Local youth are often not reflected in nor benefited by community enterprises. According to the group, a lack of economic attractiveness and an absence of real prospects for education, income, and technological innovation drive young people away from the sociobioeconomy. Productive activities, when unable to compete with urban attractions, do not have the ability for renewal.

Finally, participants highlighted Amazonian operational costs as a serious obstacle, with special emphasis on logistical conditions. The group provided concrete examples to illustrate the high costs of travel: a simple transport operation can require 500 litres of fuel, an unreachable amount without subsidies and financing adapted to local realities. In the absence

of public transport or a consolidated logistics structure, many communities need to buy their own boats to transport their products, something unthinkable within conventional business models.

External challenges

External challenges were equally difficult structurally. A lack of basic infrastructure resurfaces, this time from the perspective of connectivity with markets and services. The group noted a lack of essential public and private services, such as management consulting, technical assistance, and finance training, all of which are critical for business development. Although there are specific initiatives, there is no systematized and accessible technical support network.

Regarding public policy, the group was emphatic: the sociobioeconomy is not included in national regulatory frameworks or in fiscal incentive mechanisms. While products such as soy and cattle enjoy subsidies and exemptions, sociobiodiverse chains continue to bear high fiscal costs, making their products less competitive. Furthermore, existing regulations were created outside the Amazonian reality and do not contemplate its cultural, ecological, and productive specificities.

An absence of research and data on specific production chains also was identified as a relevant obstacle. Without clear parameters on productivity, environmental impact, and financial return, it is difficult to design effective public policies or attract investors aligned with the values of a sociobioeconomy.

In this regard, participants drew attention to the need for markets and investors to be sensitive to social and environmental impacts. The value of sociobioeconomy products goes beyond the market aspect: they protect biodiversity, conserve cultural practices, and generate ecosystem benefits such as water and landscape protection, elements that do not valued on the market but have high social value. According to group participants, applying the same risk-return logic used in the conventional economy to these sociobiodiversity products is unfair and dysfunctional. It is necessary to create a differentiated approach that values these positive externalities.

Roots of the challenges

At the end of their presentation, the group reflected on structural causes of these obstacles. First, they recognized that community enterprises operate under a different logic than conventional companies and require another, more collaborative approach with shared decision-making processes and multiple objectives, including social impact and cultural empowerment.

The group also highlighted the country's historical and exploitative logic in relation to its natural resources, with different emphases among the states of the Amazon, but with a common pattern: one-off and discontinuous projects that do not build infrastructure or long-term policies. This lack of continuity demotivates communities, undermines institutional trust, and hinders steady progress.

Group 3 – Angélica Nunes, Antonio Loboguerrero, Mayra Esseboom and Natali Silveira

Roots of the challenges

This group began by identifying that many of the obstacles faced by sociobioeconomies originate in community-level structural inequalities: deficiencies in formal education, absence of infrastructure, lack of basic services such as health and energy, and geographical isolation. These social conditions generate imbalances of power and knowledge between the different actors in a production chain, making it difficult to dialogue and build trust between parties with such different realities, such as investors and traditional communities.

In addition, they stressed that it is necessary to develop capacities not only in the territories, but also among funders and investors. Without this dual approach, solutions offered remain disconnected from reality.

Internal challenges

- The fragility of trust between community members and supporting organizations inhibits consolidation of lasting and transparent partnerships. Weak or misunderstood agreements lead to mutual frustration and discontinuous projects.
- The low administrative capacity of local organizations inhibits their autonomy. Investments in financial management, accounting, compliance with legal requirements, and financial reporting are necessary.
- Passively waiting for public policies that respond to local realities was questioned. The group suggested more incisive action to advocate for and co-construct public policies, rather than simply reacting to them.
- The perceived high risk of community-level businesses discourages investors, who end up preferring alternatives with more predictable returns.

External challenges

- The group firmly emphasized a lack of adequate mechanisms to assess positive externalities. Services such as water conservation, biodiversity protection, and carbon sequestration do not enter into return-on-investment calculations, despite their enormous social and environmental values.
- The prevailing logic of a quick return on capital is considered incompatible with existing ecological and social cycles. The challenge is to align profitability with long-term sustainability, which requires innovation in business models and investment evaluation criteria.
- Finally, the need to value any given community's own natural resources — nuts, açai, oils, seeds — which are still undervalued in the conventional market — was highlighted.

Group 4 – David Solano, Ruth Cayapa, Paulina Espin, Trent Blare and Claudio Padua

Internal challenges

The group started from the recognition that there are technical, operational and political shortcomings within local organizations themselves, which must be addressed seriously and without romanticization.

- Technical skills training in management and internal organization was identified as an essential condition. This includes everything from knowing how to handle audits to managing resources, building teams, and executing complex strategies.

- It is necessary to develop shared strategies, with genuine grassroots participation, so that projects are no longer carried out only "from the outside in".
- Clear, internal communication of goals, principles, and paths of each initiative was seen to be a recurring weakness. Without a common understanding, efforts are diffuse.
- The need to create mechanisms to retain knowledge also was highlighted. Occasional trainings occur, but trained individuals may not stay in the community or cannot apply what they have learned.
- Another challenge discussed was internal competition between groups within the same community, hoping to take advantage of the same resources. Strengthening association and cooperation between groups seems a promising path.
- Access to appropriate technologies is also an obstacle: both for use of adapted machinery and for digital platforms that facilitate production management and governance.

Figure 20 Participants presenting conclusions after the discussion in small groups.

External challenges

- There is a lack of technology adapted to sociobioeconomy realities. Platforms, software, and machinery are designed for other productive models and rarely work in Amazonian communities.
- Technical assistance continues to be offered under the logic of large agro-industrial companies, without connection to sustainable and territorial sociobioeconomy models.
- Current legal and political frameworks are incompatible with local realities. Projects often face requirements that don't make sense in the territories, and there is no institutional support to adapt these standards.
- The group also highlighted the need to diversify markets, avoiding concentration on a single product and exploring market potential of biodiversity with a broad net.

- A sensitive concern expressed was a resumption of raw extractivism without criteria, which could be used to justify deforestation and unsustainable practices.
- Finally, financing also depends on the agency of community actors themselves, who must be protagonists in search for support and resources, based on technical knowledge and strategic clarity.

Structural roots

This group's analysis also addressed systemic structures that block the advancement of a sociobioeconomy:

- The current economic system, based on profit and speed, does not recognize collaborative practices of physical exchanges and unhurried pace typical of Amazonian communities.
- The financial system is not prepared to face territorial realities: neither in terms of access nor equal treatment.
- Corruption and the illegal economy, especially mining and land grabbing, compete with grassroots initiatives and are often faster and more attractive alternatives, especially for young people.
- There is little generation of applied knowledge, although there is already a lot of scattered information. The challenge is to make this knowledge accessible and useful in the territories.
- Finally, a lack of physical and legal security in communities, compounded by escalating violence and state absence, poses a real threat to forest defenders and a livelihood-based economy.

Group 5 – Vanessa Luna, Floriana Breyer and Carlos Koury

Internal challenges

- The group drew attention to the complexity generated by the diversity of value chains in the territories. Each new product requires specific capabilities, structures, and costs, which requires a careful strategy to avoid overburdening and fragmenting of local efforts.
- The seasonality of production imposes challenges for cash flow and strategic business planning, especially to maintain financial stability and personal commitment.
- They also stressed the urgency of ensuring gender equality and youth participation. Keeping young people in the territories depends directly on creating attractive opportunities for education, employment, and self-determination.
- A critical point was the lack of planning and anticipation of risks and opportunities. The lack of strategic plans weakens the ability to make good use of available resources.
- Finally, the group underlined the importance of including the cost of environmental conservation in the value of products, but stressed that this cost should not be passed on to the end consumer.

External challenges

- The group reinforced the urgent need for adequate public policies and specific subsidies for the socioeconomic sector, which today faces an asymmetrical scenario compared to soybean and livestock sectors, for example.

- They noted the importance of forming diverse partnerships that bring together different knowledge and expertise. They stressed, however, that community-based organizations often do not have enough staff to manage complex relationships with multiple actors.
- They denounced the lack of project continuity, which generates frustration and mistrust in the communities.
- They also criticized an absence of adequate language to generate and disseminate knowledge. This hinders dialogue between science and traditional knowledge, excluding communities from innovation systems.
- They emphasized that traditional knowledge must be present from project conception, and not only as data or technical contributions. The absence of this participation is a form of epistemological exclusion.

At the end of the third day of the workshop, the plenary discussion delved into a set of structural topics for strengthening the sociobioeconomy: ethics in relations with territories, the role of universities and researchers, the challenges of managing community enterprises, and the essential role of communication as a vector of transformation. Participants from different regions and sectors contributed reflections on how to build real bridges between technical-scientific knowledge and traditional knowledge, with respect, equity, and permanence. Table 5 brings together the main challenges and roots of those challenges raised by the groups.

Table 5 Summary of the internal and external challenges of the sociobioeconomy and its roots.

Internal challenges	External challenges
Lack of time and links with indigenous communities; NGO dependency.	Inflexible funding rules and insufficient terms.
Poor management of community enterprises. Lack of generational succession.	Absence of essential public services and logistics infrastructure.
Fragility of trust and administrative capacity of local organizations.	Lack of mechanisms to value externalities and appropriately address quick return logic.
Technical and operational shortcomings in community organizations and poor internal communication.	Lack of adequate technology and incompatible legal frameworks.
Inherent value chain diversity generates chain fragmentation, seasonality challenges, and planning hurdles.	Lack of project continuity and exclusion of traditional knowledge.
Roots of the challenges	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Historical exploitative logic coupled with one-off and discontinued projects. • Structural inequalities in infrastructure, education, and basic public services. • The economic and financial system does not recognize collaborative practices. • Corruption, illegal economies, and the absence of the State in Amazonian communities. • Dispersed knowledge and a lack of physical and legal security. 	

Collective reflections

The discussion began on knowledge generation in indigenous and traditional territories, with special attention to research ethics. The group collectively opened with a harsh denunciation of the recurrent practice by researchers of extracting information without returning to communities to share results. This practice not only breaks trust, but also perpetuates an power inequalities between those who are the source of knowledge and those who make it public.

As a counterargument, positive experiences were reported, showing that feedback is possible when structured as part of the scientific process. Institutional programs highlighted included the *Morning with Science* initiative by IPÊ in Portal do Paranapanema, in which researchers regularly returned to share their findings with the local population. Another was the use of targeted funding by the University of Florida's Tropical Conservation and Development Program to ensure that graduate student researchers shared results in an accessible and respectful manner. It was agreed that ethics should be incorporated into research structures, moving beyond discourse to concrete actions.

It was recalled that many communities do not even have access to platforms where research results are published, which requires rethinking publication formats and valuing local knowledge, intercultural dialogue, and accessible language. Discussions of research findings must be an exchange of information rather than unidirectional.

In addition, the group criticized the distance between the knowledge produced in universities and the practical needs of communities. The group highlighted the need for science to be more applied and committed to social transformation, rather than focused solely on academic publications. Science must be an instrument to form and strengthen local autonomy.

The proposal to value community researchers was widely supported, including the suggestion that communities be engaged as co-researchers, knowledge producers and data analysts, capable of making decisions based on local evidence. The importance of indigenous science as a legitimate field of knowledge and action was reinforced.

The group also contributed practical experiences of technological integration, demonstrating how industrial solutions can be adapted to the Amazonian reality to improve productivity without detracting from local ways of life. This connection between innovation and territory was considered key to strengthening the sociobioeconomy. An example provided was implemented within the Uatumã Sustainable Development Reserve, where a technology used by the Manaus Industrial Pole was adapted for a local community. Three meters of rail track were enough to enable a simple machine to package plant-based oils, increasing productivity and improving product presentation. "*The technologies already exist. We need to connect the worlds,*" defended one of the participants.

Figure 21 Participants gathered for a collective discussion.

However, he warned about the challenge of community-based businesses in confronting the logic of short-term projects. Management and continuity of community-centered initiatives were identified as critical bottlenecks, as few investments center long-term sustainability. Discontinuity creates frustration, a breakdown of trust, and limits the ability of communities to sustain progress made.

The group also reflected on distribution of economic benefits derived from production chains, bringing profit to the center of the discussion. The question was "benefit for whom?", proposing that profit serve as a tool for autonomy and not one of exploitation. Financial sustainability was recognized as necessary, as long as it is balanced with values of justice and local protagonism.

Communication appeared as a strategic transversal axis. It was agreed that good examples should be made visible, inspire other territories, and help transform perceptions. Communication was treated not only as a medium, but as an input that adds value, disseminates knowledge, and articulates innovation with the market.

In addition to collective reflections, the group began to develop concrete proposals. A collective agenda guided by structured themes such as public policies, infrastructure, intergenerational valuation, and the language of knowledge was suggested. Finally, it was proposed to articulate a Pan-Amazonian network of cooperation in sociobioeconomy, which unites efforts, avoids redundancies, and accelerates the transition towards fairer, more ethical, and sustainable models.

Gender, social equity, and territorial wellbeing in Conservation Finance and Sociobioeconomies

Another panel was organized on this third workshop day to bring together voices from different territories and backgrounds to discuss how gender, youth, and territorial justice are intertwined with the challenges of Conservation Finance and strengthening of sociobioeconomies. The discuss was led by Pilar Useche, an economist and professor at the University of Florida with extensive experience in rural development and sustainable financing.

Key participants included Antonio Loboguerrero, a Colombian researcher with international experience in climate policy, food security, and sustainable rural development. Representing Suriname, Mayra Esseboom contributed her experience as a researcher, with a strong presence in indigenous and Maroon communities. From Brazil, Vanda Witoto, educator and indigenous leader of the Witoto people, highlighted the perspectives of indigenous peoples.

Figure 22 Participants during the presentation of the panel on gender and social equality.

Pilar's first question explored intergenerational relationships in the territories: "In each of your initiatives, what happens to young people? Are they being encouraged to stay in the communities or do they prefer to leave? What attracts or repels them from these territories?"

Antonio Loboguerrero brought the Colombian reality. He pointed out that many young people today move away from the territory, not only physically, but also symbolically. Many of today's leaders are over 50 years old and participated in the struggle for territory. While they retain a strong historical memory of this process, young people who grew up in later times do not share the same experience or the same ties. *"They think differently,"* Antonio said. The city seduces them with its promises: urban culture, connectivity, the so-called "American dream", or even the opportunities offered by extractive sectors such as mining companies.

This has led to a progressive abandonment of territories, despite the fact that indigenous peoples represent only 2% of the population and own 30% of the land. Traditional forms of

production (such as *chakra* or subsistence farming) are perceived as harsh, unattractive, and yielding limited results. And today's youth, as he himself said, "wants easier things, they don't want severity." Many no longer consume what they produce; they fish to sell and buy industrialized food. Even so, Antonio pointed out that well-structured Sociobioeconomy projects can offer attractive opportunities for young people to stay in the territories, even if they do not generate large immediate benefits. *"They want to stay, but under other conditions."*

The migration of young people to urban centers often pushes them into precarious conditions and places them in a "cultural limbo", where they are not fully accepted by either the traditional indigenous world or the urban world. This uprooting has serious consequences, such as the high suicide rate among indigenous youth in Colombia. *"They say that young people should listen to their elders, but no one wants to listen to young people. We need to listen to young people to understand their true needs."*

Next, Mayra Esseboom from Suriname shared a very different picture, marked by a reverse movement: the return of young people to rural communities. She explained that over the past five years, the rising cost of living in cities, combined with national economic instability, has led many young people, especially from indigenous and Maroon communities (descendants of enslaved Africans who escaped into the forest), to return to the countryside due to the lower cost of living and income-generating opportunities from fishing, agriculture, and forest management.

Mayra drew attention to the matriarchal structure of Maroon communities, where the responsibility for the children traditionally falls on the mother's siblings, which contributes to the permanence of young people in the areas of origin. By marrying young and starting a family from a young age, many perceive advantages in being in communities where they can plant, fish, live at lower costs, and, at the same time, innovate. *"Young people are coming back and this has led to innovation: they don't just want to repeat what their elders did, but to create new ways of living in the forest."*

However, a return to the countryside also faces challenges. She highlighted conflicts caused by gold mining, especially the lack of community rights within their own territories. The government grants mining concessions to third parties, preventing community members from accessing and enjoying the lands they have inhabited for generations. Young people are pushed into illegal mining, often risking their lives: *"We've already lost young people in quarry collapses,"* she said. Mayra strongly defended the need for effective action by the State, not only in intention, but also in action. *"The government must be present. It should not just try to listen, but to do. They have the means to make policy and direct investments."*

Vanda then began her story by describing her attentive listening to community elders living on the length of the Solimões River — a six-day journey that illustrates the depth and extent of the affected territories. According to Vanda, one of the most significant vectors of cultural transformation in the last 40 years has been the growing presence of fundamentalist churches in indigenous territories. This presence has displaced the symbolic and social centers of the communities: *"It is no longer the maloca that is in the center of the town, but the church, with a cross larger than the forest,"* she said. This reversal of symbolic centrality has also altered traditional hierarchies and systems of authority: the cacique loses his place of respect, being replaced by the pastor, often a young man who studies outside the territory and returns as a religious figure, promoting indoctrination.

Figure 23 Participant presenting during a panel on gender, equity, and inclusion.

This process generates, according to Vanda, a deep generational distance, in which young people no longer respect or listen to their elders, contributing to erosion of traditions and cultural memory. Young people find themselves in a "no-place" - torn between obeying the Bible or following the teachings of elders and shamans. This conflict is aggravated by demonization by the churches of indigenous rituals, languages, and songs, which for Vanda, constitutes a violent cultural transformation that breaks the sense of belonging and self-esteem of young people.

She warned of high suicide rates among indigenous youth, a direct consequence of this process of uprooting, rupture of identity, and loss of a sense of belonging. Along with religion, she also pointed to Western school education as a factor of cultural disconnection. This education distances children from collective coexistence and life in the fields, from sowing and fishing, from ancestral orality. *"Grandpa is not in the school,"* she summarized.

In addition, Vanda drew attention to the structural reasons that lead indigenous peoples to abandon their territories. Today, about 60% of the indigenous population is living outside indigenous lands, mainly in search of education, health care, and work, because the state does not offer adequate public policies within the territories. This absence of specific policies leads to forced migration and the consequent fragility of communities.

Faced with this scenario, she highlighted the autonomous actions of indigenous peoples themselves to rebuild their identity and strengthen their ways of life. One example is the creation of a self-awareness school (Atelier Derequine) in the urban indigenous community of Parque das Tribos in Manaus, aimed at preparing indigenous children before they enter a formal school. This early-learning school works to strengthen self-esteem, celebrate Indigenous designs, painted bodies, artistic knowledge, the value of raising your own food and fishing.

"Indigenous children, when they enter formal school, hear that they are ugly, dirty. On the bus, people walk away from them when they're wearing Indigenous designs."

For women, Atelier Derequine's initiative emerges as a tool for autonomy and income generation, but also as a cultural affirmation. *"We want women to feel smart, beautiful, capable, with their designs and hand-made clothes."* Finally, Vanda made an incisive critique of the reductionist view of the Amazon that appears in satellite images: *"This view only wants to protect the tree. But he doesn't want to protect people's lives."* She stressed that *indigenous bodies are the true guardians of the forest*, they are the ones who resist illegal mining, deforestation, and invasions. And she concluded with an essential warning: *"If our bodies are not cared for, with health and education, our territories will not be protected."*

Paulina commented on these oral illustrations, highlighting a common pattern observed in communities in Ecuador, that of early motherhood among indigenous girls, some as young as 12 or 13 years old. She explained how this reality distances these young women from decision-making spaces, since the role of caregivers is imposed on them very early.

"Society sees them as if life ends after having children. They are no longer considered an active part of the community and become politically invisible." According to Paulina, these girls come to be seen only as responsible for domestic care, which prevents them from developing leadership skills and participating in community management and decision-making processes. The cycle of exclusion is perpetuated when there is no community or institutional structure that allows them to reconcile motherhood and protagonism.

Next, Ruth Cayapa, speaking from the reality of her Ecuadorian community, reinforced that what Paulina described is not only a social consequence, but a deep-rooted traditional custom: *"It is customary in our territory for girls to be handed over to their partners before the age of 16. This prevents us from being in assemblies, in the spaces where decisions are made."*

Ruth was emphatic in describing how assemblies are still mostly male and how the role of women, especially the youngest, remains passive and invisible. The overload of domestic commitments and early motherhood make many girls stop looking young, such is the symbolic and material burden they carry. *"These girls are trapped in a power structure that prevents them from thinking about another future. They are children taking care of children."*

To break this cycle, Ruth defended the promotion of young female leaders, pointing out that it is necessary to *"work hard in their heads"* so that they understand that they have the right to space, voice, and recognition, in addition to their roles as mothers and caregivers. According to her, development of these young female leaders is carried out through initiatives that guarantee income, autonomy, and knowledge, essential conditions for them to occupy respected positions in their communities. Ruth also pointed out the obstacle of institutionalized sexism in community-based organizations:

"In our organization, the leaders are men, and many don't want women to become leaders. They don't want women to have knowledge, because they know that knowledge is power."

Her speech revealed that access to knowledge is not only a matter of technical training, but of power struggle, and that control of information is used as a tool to contain female leadership. She concluded by highlighting that there are young people with a vocation to lead, and that it is necessary to identify, encourage, and protect them as transformative examples in their communities.

Continuing, Pilar asked the participants: "Does intergenerational knowledge affect the role of women and inclusion in territories?" Mayra's response highlighted an important historical process of women's mobilization in the country. In the 80s, she recalls, the National Women's Organization was founded, which played a central role in the creation of women's community organizations and in raising awareness that women are fundamental in the cultural construction of their territories. *"Women are mothers, yes, but they are also leaders. They are the ones who hold communities together."*

According to Mayra, today the fruits of this mobilization are being harvested: communities with structured feminist organizations and women of different ethnicities have come to desire and fight for a space in politics, markets, and education. She noted that, increasingly, Maroon women are entering universities, motivated by a desire to contribute to their communities and transform the way they are treated socially. Many of these women return to their localities as teachers, taking with them not only the knowledge of Western education, but also traditional knowledge, in a movement that strengthens bridges between worlds. Pilar commented that these trajectories confirm what is already perceived in the field: *"Women are catalysts in the process of circulation and resignification of intergenerational knowledge."*

Figure 24 Participant presenting during a panel on gender, equity, and inclusion.

Vanda Witoto agreed and deepened the analysis by situating formal education as a movement of confrontation with the patriarchal structures historically imposed by colonization. She recalled that many Brazilian indigenous societies are of matriarchal origin, but that colonialism imposed a patriarchal model that displaced women from leadership positions. According to Vanda, the entry of indigenous women into universities is an act of resistance and reconnection with their ancestral origin, and it is also an example that inspires other women to do the same.

She cited Joênia Wapichana, the first indigenous woman to become a federal deputy in Brazil, as a symbol of this change. *"Indigenous women are occupying new spaces, but this also generates tensions. Men, in assemblies, are still the majority and often try to silence women. There is an internal power struggle."*

Vanda explained that the growth of female participation in communities is not a linear process: often, women who take a stand face resistance from men who fear losing space. In view of this, she said that, during the ATL (Terra Livre Camp), the National Articulation of Indigenous Women Warriors of Descent (ANMIGA) was created, a network aimed at producing data on femicide, domestic violence, and obstetric violence against indigenous women, issues that have historically been invisible. *"If there is no data, there are no public policies. We want to record this violence to change this reality."*

Vanda also spoke of the importance of encouraging listening and protagonism among indigenous youth, often discredited for not having "experience" in the eyes of older leaders. The way, according to her, is to strengthen organizations led by women and young people: *"Women are aggregators. They collaborate; they act collectively. With men, leadership often closes in on itself. Women, when they lead, make room for everyone."*

Antonio shared that one of the strategies adopted by his team was to train women as researchers in the area of health, recognizing their central role in the communities: *"They are the caregivers of the food, of the house, of the community. So they were more concerned and more involved than men."*

This movement was based on the understanding that men predominantly occupied the space of formal politics, while women sustained the daily life of the territories. Health, in this context, was an effective door to articulate training, empowerment, and permanence in the territory.

Antonio explained that many of the health problems arose precisely because of the need for people to leave the territory in search of resources, which weakened the local social fabric. To avoid this, specific programs were created, such as the bioeconomy linked to crafts, where the presence of women naturally stood out. However, this prominence also generated initial tensions: *"Some men were bothered by the fact that women were starting to earn money."*

It was in this context that the Indigenous Women's Meeting was born, an event that is held every two years and brings together women outside their territories to reflect together on their problems and strategies for empowerment. According to Antonio, these meetings have been strengthening communities as a whole, expanding awareness and the role of women in the processes of social transformation.

He also pointed out that in the territory where he works, women have come to occupy multiple roles, not only in basic activities such as crafts and tourism, but also as formal leaders, called "women captains."

This shift has direct implications for traditional role divisions between men and women. Antonio stressed that these transformations need to be recognized clearly and intentionally: *"Any new initiative in the community must bring about changes in these traditional roles — and this must be done in a clear way."*

He concluded by noting that access to technology, such as mobile phones, has also promoted profound cultural changes, dissolving the rigid barriers between what is "the role of men" and the "role of women".

The panel showed that gender, youth, and territorial wellbeing are inseparable dimensions in the construction of just and sustainable sociobioeconomies. The experiences shared showed that in several territories, women and young people still face deep structural barriers: the absence of specific public policies, rigid social roles, exclusion from decision-making spaces, and cultural transformations that weaken ties with traditional ways of life.

The need to create mechanisms that strengthen the role of women in communities emerged as central issues, especially through access to education, technical training, income generation, and recognition of their knowledge. Women were highlighted as caretakers of territory and culture, and also as emerging leaders, capable of mobilizing significant social transformations.

These panel discussions also showed that young people live in an intergenerational conflict aggravated by educational and religious models that break with collective and ancestral values. The exodus to the cities, the loss of cultural identity, and the increase in vulnerabilities, such as suicide among indigenous youth, were mentioned as symptoms of a forced distancing from the territory and its traditional references.

On the other hand, initiatives are emerging that seek to reverse this scenario, promoting contextualized education, a return to territory, innovation based on local culture, and a recognition of the transformative role of the new generations.

The panel also noted the urgency of reviewing gender roles and building more inclusive spaces for dialogue and decision-making, in which women and young people can safely and legitimately occupy leadership positions.

Network Mapping

The closing of the third day was marked by a discussion on cross-sectoral partnerships for continued collaboration in Sociobioeconomies and Conservation Finance, with special attention to Amazonian communities. This conversation sought to connect actors and map existing networks that already operate or can be mobilized in support of the Sociobioeconomy agenda.

Participants were divided into two groups: one with representatives from Brazil and Suriname and the other from the Andean regions (Peru, Colombia, Ecuador), to answer the central question:

"What existing networks or coalitions can this group leverage, connect with, or strengthen? And to which networks do you belong?"

The activity was carried out using flip charts and generated a diverse list of local, regional, and pan-Amazonian networks. The exercise revealed an unexplored potential for articulation, thematic convergences, and great opportunities for synergy between networks that today, operate in parallel.

Figure 25 Participants working in groups in the mapping of collaborative networks.

Overview of mapped networks

Below is a structured visual presentation with the aforementioned networks, categorized by country and predominant theme:

Table 6 Networks mapped by participants from Brazil and Suriname.

Category	Networks
Bioeconomy and conservation	Pan-Amazonian Bioeconomy Network Assobio, Osociobio, Brazil Nut Observatory, ACTO, BR-319 Observatory
Education and knowledge	EFN (Education for Nature), Saberes Sociobio, Fulbright Amazon Network
Gender and ancestry	ANMIGA – Articulation of Women Warriors of Descent
Governance and advocacy	Concertação pela Amazônia, Coalition on Climate, Forests and Agriculture, COIAB
Environmental finance and funds	REDLAC, CAFE, Conservation Finance Alliance
Infrastructure and marketing	Rede de Cantinas da Terra do Meio, Rede Origens Brasil, Collectives of Pirarucu, Rubber, and Açaí
Research and mapping	RHISA, LIRA, IUCN
Biodiversity and international exchange	International Biodiversity Network

Table 7 Networks mapped by participants from the Andean countries (Peru, Colombia and Ecuador).

Category	Networks
Gender, youth and inclusion	Network of Researchers in Gender Extension, Amazonian Youth Network, Chakra Mamas, UNOCARD, SIP – System of Initiatives for Peace
Bioeconomy and food systems	Bioeconomy Roundtable (Ecuador), McKnight Foundation, CGIAR (CIP/Andean Initiative), Chakra Group, Cacao – Forests and Peace
Education, universities and sciences	Network of Universities in Peru, INTE (Catholic University), UNAMAZ, CGSpace
Governance and public policies	Ministry of Environment and Agriculture, SERNAMP, Listen to the Amazon, Peruvian Society of Environmental Law (SPDA)
Financing and cooperation	MEC (Belgian NGOs), Agricord, DGD Program, PUCA (restaurants and chefs), CLAC (Fair Trade)
Tourism and local markets	ACOTUR, Cacao, Chakra and Chocolate Tourism Network
Monitoring and georeferencing	WWF – Environmental Monitoring Network, RAISG

Collective reflections on the value of networks

Participants highlighted the concrete benefits of participating in networks, reaffirming their role as fundamental structures for building the sociobioeconomy. Networks provide the following:

- They provide access to knowledge and the exchange of experiences among equals;
- They create bridges of contact and trust between different actors;
- They provide scale and visibility to local actions;
- They facilitate intersectoral articulation, integrating government, private sector, academia, and civil society;
- They reinforce the power of political and regulatory advocacy, allowing participation in the construction of public policies;
- Establish good practices and standards of action for the sector;
- They allow for faster and more coordinated responses to common challenges;
- They create a sense of belonging and collective motivation, as noted in the case of REDE LAC, a network with more than two decades of mutual institutional strengthening.

Figure 26 Participants working in groups on network mapping.

Closing of the day

At the end of the day, the final discussions brought a combination of realistic optimism and a sense of shared responsibility. The overall feeling was of concrete progress, despite the many challenges that remained. It was recognized that the field of sociobioeconomy has matured. Compared to the recent past, today there is already talk of working capital, access to credit, and a more consistent structuring of local companies. The gaze was not towards what is still missing, but towards what has already been conquered as a basis for moving forward.

The importance of articulation with public policies was also highlighted. With institutional structures now more receptive to the agenda, such as the existence of a (Brazilian) National Secretariat of Bioeconomy, the scenario offers new windows of opportunity. The proposed change in perspective was symbolic: financial actors should be seen as strategic partners, and not adversaries, as long as they are committed to the transformation of the model.

But optimism did not come without warnings. With the expectation of large volumes of resources circulating in the sector in the coming years, the risk of waste, inefficiency, and capture by actors not committed to the values of the sociobioeconomy also grows. The group recognized the urgency of creating governance mechanisms and support platforms that prepare territories to absorb investments in a safe, responsible, and enduring manner.

Ways to scale the Amazonian sociobioeconomy: financing, autonomy and strategic alliances

On the fourth day of the workshop, discussions revolved around one of the most critical and strategic issues of the sociobioeconomy: how to access and mobilize the financial resources needed for Amazonian community-led initiatives to thrive, to scale, and to be sustained over time. The initial plenary session was followed by group work with guiding questions that sought to unravel concrete experience of the organizations present:

- *What are initiatives doing to obtain financial resources?*
- *What needs to be done better to obtain financing with more autonomy?*
- *What skills are needed and how can they be attained?*

Group 1 – Pilar, David, Suzana, Trent, Antonio and Ruth

The first presentation presented the case of the program "Navigating entrepreneurship in the Amazon", carried out by IPÊ in the Puranga Conquista Sustainable Development Reserve. The initiative arose from a collaboration with LinkedIn, which offered financial resources to support community entrepreneurs.

Figure 27 Participants gathered to discuss in small groups.

The project differential was the attention to training and continuous monitoring: 100 entrepreneurs were identified, 11 received seed capital between USD \$3,000 to 5,000, and all went through a training process with volunteer consultants. The training covered topics such as pricing, packaging, dissemination, and financial management, with regular technical visits. The result: entrepreneurs began to manage their own projects autonomously.

Then, the experience of structuring a community cocoa chain in the Amazon was shared, made possible thanks to an international fund focused on conservation. With the arrival of a Canadian fund for the conservation of protected areas, it was possible to finance training in management, financing, innovation, and conservation. This initial fund allowed:

- Expansion to other communities;
- Legal and formal structuring of an association;
- Capture of diverse types of funding, including advances for clients and local government support for infrastructure.
- Artisanal production of chocolates with Amazonian ingredients such as ayahuasca and natural essences.

The group shared the use of a factory at night, resulting in production of 13,000 chocolate bars and the emergence of a small community business. Despite the advances, challenges related to deliverability and logistics, which resulted in the loss of some customers, highlighted the need for organizational consolidation and planned growth.

Another story highlighted the importance of articulation between companies and local producers, relaying a 2016 experience with the European Union in a project aimed at valuing ecosystem goods and services, such as pirarucu, camu-camu, and buriti palm. From a collaboration with a Peruvian beverage company, it was possible to connect the beverage industry's demand with local camu-camu producers. This bridge was made possible by a personal relationship with the company person responsible for the project. Today, the company continues to buy buriti fruits, highlighting the role of relationships and existing organization to create sustainable chains.

The relevance of language and thematic fit when seeking funding was also highlighted. In contexts where a project addresses issues considered to be the responsibility of the state, such as health care, adapting the narrative can facilitate access to resources. In one reported case, an indigenous health project was reformulated as a women's project, which allowed it to be framed within existing lines of support. Today, in a post-conflict Colombia, projects have been presented within the scope of "peace projects", an adaptation that responds to the political priorities of the moment and the financing opportunities associated with them.

Another highlight was the need for institutional formalization to guarantee access to funds. In practice, many indigenous enterprises exist, but they are not legally structured to receive financial resources. The creation of hybrid agreements, combining community-based NGOs and local businesses, was identified as a strategic solution. One example cited was the agreement with the Rainforest Foundation Norway, which signed a five-year partnership in which resources are managed from Norway, but implementation is done directly by communities with local technical support.

In addition, organizations such as Oxfam and ICM also participate in this type of model, composing what has been described as a functional international alliance. It was expressed that this architecture is successful because it distributes responsibilities in a complementary way: those who have the resources collaborate with those who have the knowledge of the territory and the capacity to execute.

The experience of long-term partnerships with international institutions has shown that this architecture is effective in building trust and continuity. The quality of the arrangement and execution is more important than the magnitude of the initiative. A small, well-implemented project can be more transformative than a large, poorly planned initiative.

Finally, the significant role played by international NGOs in project financing was highlighted. These funds have made it possible for several initiatives to function, even when promised resources are delayed. Local initiatives structured on the basis of community mobilization and the support of public authorities were presented as possible models, in which external resources come in as a catalyst rather than as a starting point.

One example cited was the construction of a community cultural center with the support of the provincial council in Ecuador. This support involved resources for the purchase of machinery and equipment and was made possible by the community itself, which organized collectively, building on what it already had in terms of space and structure.

This collaborative construction between community and government illustrates a model of action based on local mobilization, where external financial resources are complementary and not central. However, even with this solid foundation, there are times when the absence of working capital hinders progress, especially when initiatives need to scale or be structured more robustly.

This recognizes that small local funds are often more agile, accessible, and better adapted to the initial phase of projects, but many of them remain underutilized due to a lack of information or articulation between communities and government agencies.

Group 2 - Vanessa, Karen, Vanda, Cláudio, Andrea, Renato and Floriana

The group began its presentation by highlighting that true autonomy, especially in the context of the sociobioeconomy, can only be built through collaboration between different actors such as NGOs, the private sector, foundations, academic institutions and community-based organizations. This kind of multi-actor collaboration was championed as a strategic path to strengthen legitimacy, expand support networks, and attract resources in a more structured and sustainable way.

Figure 28 Participants met to discuss in small groups.

The group reinforced in its presentation the importance of legal formalization. Even if projects are family- or community-based, it is essential to formally register the collaboration to receive funding, establish alliances, and be part of support networks. This formalization does not have to be bureaucratic or limiting, but strategic, allowing safe entry into the financing ecosystem. Another proposal put forward by the group was the creation of collective funds within the communities themselves. The idea is that these funds will serve as mutual support mechanisms, capable of allowing small investments in early project stages when access to external credit is still difficult.

The experience of building bridges with companies was widely debated. Investors are reluctant to engage with civil society organizations, and that is why it is necessary to learn to speak executive language and adjust the project narrative and presentation. One example shared was an initiative to establish creative councils with business executives. One participant shared the experience of an organization that created an informal council that invited mid-level executives to attend monthly dinners with the organization's staff, where they exchanged ideas and strategic suggestions without any legal commitment. Over time, these executives became involved and began acting as formal advisors to the organization, opening doors, accessing networks, and helping to drive productive new ideas. This example shows that, in addition to looking for large donors, it is possible to activate collaborative networks with key people, who feel part of the process and want to invest time, knowledge, and social capital.

Another example is an enduring collaboration between IPÊ and the flip-flop brand Havaiana. A direct result of a strategy to engage and build trust between two worlds that do not traditionally talk to each other gave rise to a line of Havaiana products with an Amazonian identity.

Another recurring theme was the importance of key connections in fundraising. The group stressed that good projects are not always enough. Often, the difference is in knowing who can open doors, offer referrals, or point out pathways. In this sense, it is essential to strengthen relationships of trust with representatives of foundations, technicians from development agencies, and impact investors.

This group's discussion also differentiated between non-reimbursable and reimbursable funds. The former were considered more suitable for early entrepreneurial phases, when organizations are still developing their institutional capacities. The latter, such as lines of credit or impact investments, were seen as useful tools for established organizations. The group warned of the risks of accessing resources beyond the capacity to execute, which can lead to frustration and institutional attrition. The recommendation was clear: seek alliances and act in consortia when necessary, leveraging the experience of partners to gain scale and capacity.

Another key point was the need for mentoring to access resources, something that is often neglected. Mentoring is not limited to technical guidance, but includes training in financial education, planning and accountability, essential dimensions to ensure the longevity and integrity of organizations.

The group also pointed to a severe shortage of accountants willing to work with businesses without existing capital. Many of the bureaucratic obstacles faced by Amazonian associations and cooperatives stem from the lack of information or the lack of preparation of accountants to deal with associations and/or community sectors. Many groups, when trying to formalize their operations, face obstacles that could be solved with a trained accountant. Instead, they receive insufficient guidance that limits their ability to operate legally, access public notices, or render accounts properly.

It is necessary to bring accounting professionals closer to Amazonian realities. The group cited experiences of funding sources that operate directly with communities, without institutional intermediaries, thanks to community organizational maturity built through technical and political support over time. These cases demonstrate that it is possible to establish direct financing relationships, provided there is preparation, trust, and follow-up.

The group also highlighted the importance of incorporating risk management from the beginning of project design, considering climate, economic and governance factors as integral parts of the strategy, and not just as external threats. This preventive approach strengthens initiative resilience and sustainability.

Organizing exchanges between communities also was highlighted as a powerful tool for horizontal learning, exchange of experiences, and mutual recognition of local solutions. The logic of cooperation, rather than competition, was pointed out as a basis for strengthening collective protagonism and generating a diversity of solutions adapted to the territories.

The discussion also highlighted the importance of economic feasibility studies and the inclusion of conservation costs in product valuation. This requires appropriate tools and accurate data on each production chain. The need for seed funds, such as PRONAP in Peru, was presented as a positive example that could be replicated, both by governments and private actors.

The group critically reflected on the decolonization of funding, suggesting a transition from considering communities as "beneficiaries" to "partners". This implies a profound change of

perspective: communities not only as recipients of resources, but as co-authors of projects, with a voice, decision-making, and management.

Additionally, the concept of collective autonomy was highlighted. The idea was to demystify the notion of autonomy as absolute independence. Instead, the group defended an autonomy built on networks and based on cooperation, shared decision-making, and co-responsibility. The word "partner" has been redefined as a symbol of parity and mutual commitment, although the term generates confusion in some contexts.

The group reported that some communities express their autonomy by refusing to be accountable according to externally-generated models. This should not be interpreted as irresponsibility, but as a defense of self-determination and their own management criteria.

Finally, the group addressed the challenge of communicating with different audiences, from communities to investors. The ability to translate languages, expectations, and goals was recognized as strategic to create real bridges and avoid misunderstandings. In this process, NGOs were seen as essential mediators, able to adapt approaches and strategies to ensure that the territorialized sociobioeconomy is understood and supported. The formation of inter-agency consortia was suggested as an effective tool to strengthen projects, scale up, and ensure technical and financial support. The recommendation was to build these alliances based on existing networks, taking advantage of synergies and respecting the times and needs of the territories.

Final reflections of the plenary session

The discussion throughout the day highlighted fundamental aspects for the strengthening and expansion of the Amazonian sociobioeconomy, based on practical experiences and collective reflections. Participants provided concrete examples of fundraising and financing, revealing possible paths for the development of community businesses and local initiatives. Key points covered include:

1. Autonomy as a collective construction

- Autonomy is not isolation. It is built through cooperation with NGOs, the private sector, academia, and the State.
- The notion of "partner" was redefined as a horizontal partner and co-responsible for decisions, not just as an investor or beneficiary.
- "Collective autonomy" implies shared management, local protagonism, and interdependent pacts.

2. Institutional Strategic Architecture

- Formalization is key, even for family or community businesses, as it allows access to funds, public notices, and partnerships.
- Local community funds can secure seed capital and provide greater security in the early stages of a project.
- Hybrid structures (NGOs, associations, partner companies) strengthen the capacity to receive, execute, and account for complex financing.

3. Smart and Scalable Financing

- Non-reimbursable grant funds are better suited for initial stages and organizational strengthening.
- Repayable, reimbursable funds (such as credit and impact investing) require administrative maturity of local businesses.
- Access to resources must be supported by an ability to execute.
- Ongoing technical mentoring (planning, accounting, financial reckoning) is essential for institutional longevity.

4. Accounting and Community Governance

- Conventional accountants are not prepared to support association and community models. It is urgent to bring trained professionals closer to community realities.
- NGOs have acted as bridges between communities and specialized technical services.
- Financial accountability is considered an indicator of institutional maturity.

5. Private Sector Partnerships: Trust and Language

- Relationships with companies were made possible through creative counsels and informal meetings.
- Speaking executive language made it easier to build bridges with investors who are often reluctant to deal with civil society organizations.
- Successful alliances were born from trust built over time, which resulted in co-branding and products with an Amazonian identity.

6. Financial Education and Economic Viability

- Training in financial education is essential to empower local organizations.
- Economic feasibility studies by each specific production chain help define real costs, margins, and added value.
- Ecosystem services need to be included in pricing and market strategies.

7. Risk Management and Strategic Planning

- Climate, economic, and political risks must be mapped from the start of projects.
- Strategic planning ahead of time combined with flexibility reduces vulnerabilities.
- National and local seed funds (such as PRONAP in Peru) are effective and can be replicated.

8. Networks, consortia and inter-territorial learning

- The construction of multisectoral consortia (NGOs, private sector, banks, academia) strengthens the technical structure of initiatives and the confidence of investors.
- Exchanges between communities foster horizontal learning and strengthen territorial cohesion.
- The strengthening of regional and/or binational networks may better respond to joint risks and opportunities.

9. Decolonization of Financing

- The shift in the role of communities from "beneficiaries" to co-authors of projects promotes equity in decisions.

- Local ownership is a condition for true sustainability, and not merely a formal requirement for public notice.

Workshop Closing

With most participants still present, a moment of reflection and closure ensued. The proposal was to review the central objectives of the meeting and assess, individually and collectively, the extent to which the three and a half days of work had managed to make progress in relation to these objectives.

The facilitator recalled that the workshop began with two provocative questions: "How can the current economy be transformed into society and economy?" and "How can Conservation Finance support this transition?" These questions served as an initial basis and, throughout the workshop, were reinterpreted, adapted, and deepened by the participants themselves, in dialogue with their realities and practical experiences. He also recalled the three main objectives of the workshop:

1. Exchange and disseminate practical experiences of innovative initiatives in Sociobioeconomies and Conservation Finance;
2. Strengthen and catalyze networks, paying attention to generational and intercultural diversity;
3. Encourage each participant to leave with a new idea and at least one useful connection created during the workshop.

In addition to these, the facilitator took up the specific objectives of the meeting: to discuss the current scenario of initiatives; identify challenges and tensions; share concrete experiences; develop synergies between the sociobioeconomy and conservation; harvest applicable lessons; and, above all, to generate trust among the participants.

Each participant was then asked to retrieve their notes where, at the beginning of the workshop, they had written down their personal expectations. After a brief reading in a circle, there was a moment of silence and individual reflection where each participant was encouraged to think about whether their personal goals had been achieved.

The workshop then moved to the IPÊ garden, where the flipcharts generated during the three days were placed on the ground, organized by date and theme. This activity provided participants with a space to reconnect to the collective pathway of the workshop, to literally walk through the material, revisiting the debates, challenges, and ideas mapped in groups.

Figure 29 Participants revisiting the materials created during the three days of the workshop.

Back in the room, a dynamic ensued aimed at continuity of the connections generated during the encounter. Several proposals arose spontaneously among the participants, demonstrating the concrete desire to keep ties alive and productive. Among the suggestions recorded:

- Conduct a follow-up webinar in three to six months;
- Maintain the WhatsApp group, with use restricted to the exchange of information, actions, learning, and requests for support related to the sociobioeconomy;
- With collective consent, exchange of emails and telephones of all participants;
- Create a shared document with links to the organizations represented at the workshop;
- Prepare a report on the workshop process to be produced by IPÊ with a possible future request for more detailed information on projects shared;
- Bring products from community initiatives (such as chocolates) to upcoming meetings;
- University of Florida students can collaborate on participants' projects, especially during the academic summer;
- Produce short videos for YouTube with images and testimonies captured by the hired photographer and videographer;
- Create pairs who can mutually accompany each other as a way to stimulate continuity of actions and exchanges after the workshop.

At the end, the facilitator thanked everyone, highlighting the quality of workshop discussions, the generosity of participant testimonials, and their commitment to collective construction of solutions and paths towards a fairer, more effective sociobioeconomy linked to conservation.

Figure 30 Group of participants in the workshop on Sociobioeconomies and Conservation Finance.

Appendix

A. Complete and detailed workshop agenda

Calendar	Session	Objectives	Activities	Details
Day 1 – May 28, 2025				
Guidelines and Trust Building				
7:30-8:20	BREAKFAST			
8:30	Opening and welcome	Create a welcoming atmosphere	Welcome	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opening: Padua welcome to IPÊ (15 min.) • UF: Welcome by Karen Kainer from UF/Moore – (10 min.) • Presentation of the facilitators – Denyse Mello and Jon Dain
9:00	Presentations		Presentations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participants: (30 min) • Mark the name/location on the map of the Amazon basin using sticky notes (where you live, work) • Organization/Position
9:30	Welcome to the Topic Leader		Welcome remarks by IPE and IPC	Claudio Padua (IPE - Brazil) and Trent Blare (International Potato Center - Ecuador) (10 min)
9:45	POC: Project Overview	Alignment between participants	Context of the project: why this workshop?	Project summary with schematic drawing – Karen Kainer/UF (10 min.)
10:05	Objectives, agenda and guiding questions of the workshop		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agenda/Objectives and Logistics • Expectations • Standards 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workshop guiding questions*; objectives, agenda, logistics, etc. – Denyse (15 min.) • Expectations presented (from the virtual pre-workshop meeting); Additional expectations discussed or included by those who did not attend the virtual meeting. • Standards* – Denyse (5 min.) • Social Media Policy/Discussion Confidentiality <p>*Guiding questions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How can today's economies be transformed into sociobioeconomies? • How can Conservation Finances support the transition to sociobioeconomies? <p>Guiding principles</p>

				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bring something useful (method, approach, case, lesson learned) • Come out with something useful (method, approach, case, lesson learned) • Make a new connection that you keep
10:35	BREAK			Note: Welcome to the newcomer participant (David Solano Cornejo)
10:50	Definition of terms: "sociobioeconomy" and Conservation Finance	Common understanding of Amazonian socioeconomics and Conservation Finance (Objective 1)	Small Group Discussion: How do they look or feel in each country?	<p>Individual writing/reflection (10 min)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What do sociobioeconomies mean for you or your organization? • What does conservation finance mean for you/your organization? • What are your personal connections to the topics? What do you bring to this workshop that can benefit others? <p>Small groups (4-5 people) discuss and record in flipcharts (60 min)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What do we mean by sociobioeconomies? In Brazil? Peru? Colombia? Suriname? Ecuador? Bolivia? USA? • What do we mean by Conservation Finance?
12:00	LUNCH			
14:00	A Common Understanding of Socioeconomic Policies and Conservation Finance in the Amazon (Obj. 1)		Sharing of small group discussions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Share in the middle of group discussions in small groups • Dynamics: stretching exercises • Report of the morning discussions: Sharing in plenary by groups (90 min) • One question at a time, groups share <p>Discussion in plenary</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>What do we mean by sociobioeconomies?</i> 2. <i>What do we mean by Conservation Finance?</i> 3. <i>What are our connections to each of them?</i>
15:30	BREAK			
15:50	Fitting the pieces together		Cont.	Plenary Discussion: Bringing together Common Elements/Principles (25 min)
16:15	Reflections	(Goal 3)	Participants share opinions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Review: Now that the topics are defined and understood: • What do each of you bring to this workshop that can benefit others?
16:45-17:00	Conclusion		Discussion in plenary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What we did today: review of the day's activities and objectives • Conclusions?

				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tomorrow's agenda • Thank you to the translators, IPE team, Angelica, Analu, Vanessa • Find someone you haven't spoken to yet and introduce yourself
19:00	DINNER			
Day 2 – May 29, 2025				
Exploring the Challenges: Identifying Tensions and Leverage Points				
8:30	Openness		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Looking Back / Looking Forward 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Brief Review of Day I and Introduction to the Day II Agenda + Guiding Questions • Opening: Round - Something you're grateful for • Introduction/welcome to Suzana Padua
9:00	Panel: Interviews with participants	(Objectives 2 and 3)	<p>Sociobioeconomies from the perspective of different sectors; Interviews: the NGO</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Community/Territory o Private sector <p>(Goal 3)</p>	<p>Interviews (interactive): Sociobioeconomies from the perspective of different sectors:</p> <p>9:00 Trent Blare interviews NGO representatives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Carlos Koury • Paulina Espin <p>9:40. Interviews with Claudio Padua – Community Representatives</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advaldo Dias • Ruth Cayapa <p>Guiding Questions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Initiative: name, type, where? Objectives?</i> • <i>Specific need or opportunity? With/for whom? How did you identify yourself?</i> • <i>How did the plan develop? Where did the resources and financing come from?</i> • <i>Role of local people in the initiative?</i> • <i>How does the initiative work?</i> • <i>Key elements or practices that made it successful?</i> • <i>Challenges and tensions that are faced?</i> • <i>Strategies to overcome them?</i>
10:45	BREAK			

11:00	Panel	(Objective 2 and 3)	Sociobioeconomies; Interviews	<p>11:00 Interviews with Trent Blare – NGO Representatives: Private Sector</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Andrea Ortiz de Zevallos • Claudio Padua <p>11:40 a.m. - Plenary Discussion</p>
12:00	LUNCH			
13:50	Panel	Objective 4	Conservation finance and researcher; Interviews	<p>13:50 Interviews with Claudio Padua – Private Sector/ Conservation Finance</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Marcelo Cwerner • Manoel Serrão Bores de Sampaio <p>14:45 Dynamic: Find a partner – Find a tree outside, tap on it, exchange birthdays and return to the room. Ronda – shares anniversary dates. 3 minutes!</p> <p>14:55 Interview with Pilar Useche – Researchers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • David Solano Cornejo • Renato Farias <p>Guiding Questions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Initiative: name, type, where? Objectives?</i> • <i>Specific need or opportunity? With/for whom? How did you identify yourself?</i> • <i>How did the plan develop? Where did the resources and financing come from?</i> • <i>Role of local people in the initiative?</i> • <i>How does the initiative work?</i> • <i>Key elements or practices that made it successful?</i> • <i>Challenges and tensions that are faced?</i> • <i>Strategies to overcome them?</i>
15:50	BREAK			

16:05	Small Group Discussion	(Goal 3)	Common challenges and "tensions"	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analysis of interviews with 10 people: • Small groups of mixed sectors: What were the main challenges (internal and external) that we heard today? The tensions? Note it in the flipchart. • Have they been contacted? How? • What have we heard that worked? What didn't work? Why?
16:40	Plenary	(Goal 3)	Returning to topics	Groups Present + Questions and Answers Q&A factors that influenced success
17:15	Conclusion		Discussion in plenary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What did we do today? • Conclusions? • Agenda for tomorrow • Something you'll request or someone you'll contact
19:00	DINNER			
20:00	FRATERNIZATION			
Day 3, May 30, 2025				
Scalable, ethical, inclusive, and equitable approaches				
8:30	Fly-half (Jon)		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Looking Back / Looking Forward 	<p>Opening:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Who sang last night? • What did we do yesterday? Why? • Festa Junina "Great March" • Presentation of the agenda of the third day + objectives of the third day/guiding questions • Next important meeting/activity you have? • Definition of "Scale" (Trent)
8:45	Small Group Discussion			Discussion on the results of yesterday's session. 5 Groups
9:35				Discussion in plenary
10:30	BREAK			
10:4		Objective 5	How are the socioeconomic management and financing of gender conservation,	<p>Interviews with Pilar Useche – Issues of gender, equity, territoriality and integration</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mayra Esseboom • Vanda Witoto

			social equality and territorial/cultural sovereignty taken into account? Avoid being "captured by the elite." (Goal 5)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Antonio Loboguerero <p>Guiding Questions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>How are gender, social equity, and territorial/intercultural wellbeing included in socioeconomic and Conservation Finance?</i> <i>What knowledge (how to add value beyond extraction) do we need for an inclusive sociobioeconomy that benefits everyone, avoiding "capture by the elite"?</i> <i>What strategies have been successful?</i>
12:00	LUNCH			
13:45	Plenary		Cont. (Goal 4)	<p>Dynamic: Walk around the room and greet people as if you were a friend, dancer, toddler, celebrity, etc.</p> <p>Discussion: What have we learned that can help SMEs become a more important part of established economies? What steps can be taken? <i>Concrete examples</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Couples discuss "I did X and it worked*" (10 min) Plenary Discussion: Peer Report (80 min) <p>*Without being dominated by this market (getting lost in the process, captured by the elite, losing the essence of sociobioeconomies, small companies versus large companies?)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Adevaldo: Logistics of fish transport</i> <i>Mayra: Organization of women's groups</i> <i>Carlos: Blockchain</i> <i>Andrea: Ice factory and product diversification</i>
15:30	BREAK			
15:45	Small Groups Plenary		Networks and coalitions: Cross-sectoral alliances for continued collaboration on socioeconomic efforts and	<p>What networks or coalitions are there that this group could take advantage of, that it could partner with? Which chains do you belong to?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Small groups per country make lists (20 min)

			Conservation Finance, with special attention to Amazonian communities. (Goal 6)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Report/sharing in plenary (60 min)
17:30	Conclusion			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> What did we do today? Conclusions? Tomorrow's agenda Something you'll share with a partner when you get home <p>Tomorrow they leave: Marcelo, Advaldo, Myra, Manoel</p> <p><i>PARTICIPATORY EVALUATION: Did you feel that you contributed an innovative idea? Have you learned something new that you will share with others? Will it influence what you do? Have you made any new useful contacts?</i></p>
19:00	DINNER			
Day 4 – May 31, 2025 From inspiration to action				
8:30	Openness		Looking Back / Looking Forward	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Openness: "Think of a place in the Amazon that you'd love to show people if you could." Feedback round/share. Brief overview of Day III <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Report on challenges/tensions Debate on gender, equity and generational/youth challenges (Mayra, Vanda, Antonio) Examples of effective projects Discussion on networks Presentation of the agenda of the fourth day + who left yesterday (4 yesterday, 2 this morning) Guiding questions

9:15	Plenary		Resources to scale and move forward	<p>Facilitating plenary</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What does it take for local organizations to raise funds for themselves? • What are you doing since it has worked? • What skills are necessary for SME efforts to be successful and how can they be developed?
10:30	BREAK			
11:00	Miscellaneous	Facilitated Synthesis, Closing Circle	Fitting the pieces together Summary and conclusions	<p>Workshop Review and Evaluation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Review of the questions and guiding objectives of the workshop • Review of topics and activities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Gallery tour - in pairs (place all the flipcharts around the IPE circular garden, outside). Comment on your reflections as you review the workshop – 15 minutes. <p>11:30 Go back to the meeting room, look for flip charts/post-its with your personal goals for the workshops. In pairs: did you reach them?</p> <p>11:45</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What subsequent actions/actions would benefit YOU and your colleagues? (Follow-up workshops in each country for those who could or could not attend?) • What products will be produced/shared (Analu) <p>What should be shared at the February summit? What should be shared through other channels in this workshop? Social networks? Networks? How will you share what you've learned here? What connections did you make?</p> <p>Evaluation – in writing</p>
12:25	Plenary		Closing	<p>Closing remarks/closing (thematic leaders, UF) Thanks to the translators, Claudio/Suzana-IPE, Trent/Claudio/Pilar. Analu, Vanessa, Angelica, Denyse and all participants CLOSING</p>
13:00	CELEBRATORY LUNCH			